

Annex: 1

PSYCHOLOGICAL INTERVENTIONS

Landscape of psychological and social interventions for anxiety, depression and psychosis and recommendations for investment to advance the field.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACCEPTANCE AND COMMITMENT THERAPY (ACT).....	1
COMMON ELEMENTS TREATMENT APPROACH (CETA).....	8
EYE MOVEMENT DESENSITISATION AND REPROCESSING THERAPY (EMDR)	16
INTERPERSONAL PSYCHOTHERAPY (IPT)	25
ISLAMIC TRAUMA HEALING (ITH).....	32
MINDFULNESS-BASED INTERVENTIONS (MBI).....	38
PROBLEM MANAGEMENT PLUS (PM+).....	49
PROBLEM SOLVING THERAPY (PST).....	57

ACCEPTANCE AND COMMITMENT THERAPY (ACT)

Pipeline stage: Improve and Test

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Assistant Professor in Nursing, researching developments of ACT, China
- ACT therapist and trainer, and university tutor on an advanced course in ACT, UK
- Practising ACT therapist and clinical psychologist, Brazil
- Clinical Psychologist working with a United Nations organisation, Switzerland
- Professor of Clinical Psychology and Advisor to the US Government on Mental Health, USA

Target disorders:

ACT has a broad applicability, since the psychological skills promoted by it may be enhanced in any domain in life regarding unwanted thoughts, feelings and physical sensations, meaning that it can be relevant to multiple mental health conditions. ACT is widely endorsed as a treatment for depression, psychosis, chronic pain and mood disorders (Dindo et al, 2017).

Overview of intervention:

ACT is a psychological intervention that combines awareness and acceptance strategies with commitment and behaviour change techniques to enhance psychological flexibility. The goal of the therapy is to help clients shift their relationship with their experiences by reducing avoidance and inflexibility and engaging more fully in a meaningful, value-driven life. ACT is grounded in mindfulness, which involves being consciously aware of the present moment with openness, curiosity, acceptance, and without judgment. The primary aim of the therapy is to increase psychological and behavioural flexibility, particularly in areas where experiential avoidance limits a person's ability to function effectively across different aspects of life (Alirahmi et al., 2024).

Scope:

The aim of this review is to consider key factors that have facilitated the development and use of ACT, along with issues that have served as barriers to its wider scaling and adoption. It is currently classified at the Improve and Test stage of development given the continued and substantive focus on refinement of the approach and modalities of delivery. We seek to identify gaps in knowledge that, if addressed, could support advance of ACT towards the Scale and Adoption stages of the development pipeline.

Intervention development and theory of change:

ACT is a psychological intervention, originating from the cognitive behavioural psychotherapy tradition, that became a key component of the "third wave" as it introduced change processes like acceptance, cognitive diffusion, mindfulness, and values into evidence-based therapeutic practices. It has been suggested that ACT was thus not so much a technological addition to CBT but a fundamental shift in its core principles (Hayes and King, 2024).

The intervention was originally called 'Comprehensive Distancing' (CD), which is a term inspired by Aaron Beck's use of "distancing" to describe the process of stepping back to observe internal experiences in order to be able to consider different perspectives. In CD, distancing was considered a goal in itself or a

central feature of psychological flexibility, but in CBT it was used mainly as a way to lay the groundwork for addressing cognitive distortions and deficiencies (Hayes and King, 2024).

An interviewee who is an experienced ACT trainer suggested that the core principles of the approach are relatively straightforward, noting that *'despite all the different ACT books aimed to support people with sleep difficulties, worry, depression, anxiety, trauma and so on, the intervention basically works the same way. However, this does not mean that it is easy to do'*. The Association of Contextual Behaviour Science is the organisation established to promote the understanding and use of ACT, and provides information on training in ACT, including its brief forms such as focused ACT and working with the ACT matrix.

The global dissemination of ACT has been significantly influenced by the development of the guided self-help programme Self-Help Plus (SH+) by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021). SH+ is a 5-session, group-based transdiagnostic intervention based on ACT, designed to assist adults in managing stress and adversity based by helping them to accept difficult emotions and thoughts while taking actions aligned with their values.

An increasing focus for ACT is the management of physical impairment and medical illnesses such as cancer, diabetes and multiple sclerosis (Konstantinou et al. (2023). Many studies of ACT also address aspects of behavioural health such as weight loss, exercise, smoking and substance abuse, performance (academic, workplace or athletic), aspects of parenting (Ganjari and Nourimoghadam, 2024; Alirahmi et al. 2024) and social issues. The 'centre of gravity' of work on ACT is thus now well beyond the field of mental disorder and the focus of this review (Hayes and King, 2024).

From the perspective of ACT, psychological disorders are considered to stem from psychological inflexibility. ACT posits that individuals often find their inner feelings, emotions, or thoughts distressing and continuously try to change or eliminate them, but these attempts to control emotions are generally ineffective and, paradoxically, can intensify the very feelings, emotions, and thoughts that individuals seek to avoid. The core process of ACT, therefore, focuses on teaching individuals how to disengage from their thoughts, not to get entangled with disturbing thoughts, and to become more tolerant of unpleasant emotions (Alirahmi et al, 2024).

Efficacy and effectiveness:

The publication of randomised controlled trials (RCTs) of ACT has significantly accelerated in the last decades, with over 90% of studies published since 2012 (Hayes and King, 2024). The Association of Contextual Behavioural Science regularly collates evidence regarding the efficacy and effectiveness of ACT and currently documents over 500 meta-analyses and over 1,000 RCTs (ACBS, 2025). These cover a wide range of human issues, extending well beyond traditional diagnostic categories.

The efficacy of ACT with respect to the target disorders of anxiety, depression and psychosis is rated in each case as having 'modest research support' with respect to the criteria of the American Psychological Association (ICBS, 2025). This represents evidence from one or more well-designed studies, but falling below the 'strong research support' threshold established through 'well-designed studies conducted by independent investigators ... converg[ing] to support a treatment's efficacy'. The ratings of the Australian Psychological Society similarly rate evidence for ACT use to address anxiety, depression and psychotic disorders at 'level II', and thus weaker than the 'level I' evidence established through 'a meta-analysis or a systematic review of level II studies that included a quantitative analysis' (ICBS, 2025).

In terms of specific meta-analyses, Dimidjian et al. (2016) summarise findings from eight major studies noting – with respect to diverse psychopathologies - reported effect sizes in the medium range (0.50-0.79)

when compared to wait list or treatment as usual or in the medium range or no effect to small range (0.00-0.49) when compared to other cognitive or behavioural interventions.

In interpreting this evidence and its influence on practice, one stakeholder interviewed noted: *'ACT is intuitive. As a therapist you can pick up the key ideas quickly, and with some clients you will see quick results...which is encouraging for client and therapist. APC can bring immediate relief to some clients, but I don't consider it a good match for people with serious mental disorders who need extended treatment and support'*.

Psychosis, however, has been a recent focus of feasibility trials. Gaudio et al. (2023) are exploring use of ACT by hospital staff as part of acute treatment with a view to reducing rates of rehospitalisation. Özer and Dissiz (2024) are examining the effect of online group-based ACT on individuals with early psychosis, focusing on psychotic symptoms and functionality levels

Meanwhile, SH+ has been another focus of work on establishing effectiveness of this modality as a means of delivering ACT. Karyotaki et al. (2023) provided an individual participant data meta-analysis drawing from three RCTs of SH+ with refugee and asylum seeker populations with low risk of bias. They found significant short-term effects on reporting symptoms of depression, but these were not sustained to a significant degree post-intervention. They conclude that identifying specific groups who may gain the most from this intervention would help ensure its more targeted and effective implementation.

Relevance to PLE:

Reflecting principles of mindfulness, ACT has proven popular with populations that find such approaches accessible and meaningful. During consultations, PLE representatives spoke favourably of their experience – and of others in their member associations – regarding such approaches compared to other psychological interventions. One person who had experience of ACT noted how, during the COVID-19 pandemic, it had helped them accept the limits of their control over circumstances. They had also experienced it as queer affirming: *'So as a queer person, I think of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy when I know that I cannot change certain things about myself, when I know ... what I cannot change about the society existing around me ...knowing that - and a practitioner reaffirming that - has been very helpful for me and has definitely been very helpful for depression'*. The accessibility of ACT was reinforced by an interviewed stakeholder who noted: *'The approach of ACT is in line with many Eastern understandings and is thus accessible to populations that can find methods like CBT – for example, in relation to the idea of 'automatic thoughts' – very difficult to understand. There's a challenge with both language and ideas with CBT, but these are much reduced with ACT'*.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

Analysis by the Washington State Institute for Public Policy concludes on the basis of meta-analyses and cost studies that the benefit-to-cost ratio of a course of ACT treatment for anxiety is 61.42, with an 85% chance that provision will produce benefits greater than costs (WSIPP, 2025). Their analysis in relation to a course of ACT treatment for psychosis indicates a much lower level of cost-effectiveness with an estimated benefit-to-cost ratio of 1.81 and a 48% chance that provision will produce benefits greater than costs. These figures reflect clinician and patient costs and benefits associated with labour and social conditions in the USA. Clearly the benefit-to-cost ratio in other settings will vary significantly dependent upon local values of these parameters.

The relevance of local participant labour costs and benefits to analysis of cost-effectiveness – and thus the contextual relativity of cost-benefit ratios - is well illustrated in a recent study by Witlox et al. (2022) in the Netherlands. Their health-economic evaluation in older adults with anxiety symptoms found that there

is no significant difference between the ACT and CBT interventions in terms of treatment responders and quality-adjusted life year gains over a one-year period, but in economic terms, a blended ACT intervention (a combination of an online self-help module with face-to-face sessions with a mental health counsellor) had a slight advantage over CBT since it is associated with lower productivity costs (Witlox et al., 2022).

Context, applicability and scalability:

ACT has broadly shown applicability across different cultures, with empirical studies documenting use in North and South Americas, Africa, Asia, Europe and Australia. This indicates strong potential for cross-cultural adaptation (Gloster et al, 2020). Members of the Global Advisory Board for this project – when discussing prioritisation of interventions - shared their experience of the value of ACT, suggesting it to be simple to operationalise and often easier to secure fit with local culture than, for example, cognitive therapy.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

Hayes and King (2024) note the breadth of international research engagement in the development and use of ACT. While the bulk of studies continue to be based on work in Europe and the Americas, considering non-indexed journals have document 307 studies in Iran, 59 studies in China, 56 studies in South Korea and 11 studies in India. Across indexed and non-indexed journals, some 463 ACT-related studies are based on work in LMICs.

ACT has been shown to be of relevance to marginalised communities in many settings, including LMICs. For example, a cluster randomised trial examined the effectiveness of ACT delivered via SH+ in reducing psychological distress in female refugees. Results indicated a small but significant effect size on psychological distress, suggest that the intervention may be highly suitable as a first-line intervention for large populations exposed to significant stressors, such as refugees and other people exposed to adverse situations, in low-resource settings (Tol et al., 2020).

Given its aim to ‘increase psychological flexibility, consisting of an open and aware orientation to one’s experiences, and an engaged approach to living, guided by personal values’ (Williams and Samuel, 2024), ACT has been suggested as a particularly suitable intervention to address psychological distress related to climate change (Bellehumeur et al., 2024).

Despite the congruence of Eastern concepts with many of the features of ACT noted earlier, an interviewee working in China noted that many of the tools used with the approach nonetheless reflected Western understandings. These need to be modified for use in contexts with different cultural assumptions and values. She suggested it was particularly important to find language and metaphors that helped clients connect with their emotional experience, especially when talking about emotions may not be culturally normative. It was observed that this may be less of a challenge with SH+, which presents ACT concepts in a more concrete manner.

Recent years have seen increasing interest in the potential of internet-based delivery of ACT (e.g. Zhang et al., 2021), which promises a clear mechanism for provision at scale.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

ACT faces several barriers that hinder its expansion and wider adoption. One interview suggested that a major barrier is resistance from mental health professionals who are more familiar and comfortable with approaches, such as CBT. The experiential and mindfulness-based nature of ACT can be perceived as less objective by some therapists and patients, which may hinder its acceptance. A combination of wide public interest in its application in relation to general wellbeing, inconsistent findings within the current evidence-base and the values-based understanding at the core of the approach, appears to have rendered

ACT a particularly contested intervention (McKay and O'Donohue, 2023). As one interviewee with experience of both clinical training and national mental health policy guidance noted: '*Organisations like XXX are more conservative, favouring CBT and seeing ACT as something of a fad...but students are really keen to learn it*'.

Limited training opportunities, particularly outside the discipline of psychology, were noted by an interviewee from a nursing background, eager to make ACT accessible as a treatment option across a broader range of health professionals.

While ACT has been disseminated widely through SH+, one experienced ACT trainer interviewed suggested its protocol-based approach may not fully communicate the principles required to achieve the psychological flexibility targeted in therapy, especially as a current shift in ACT research is towards process-based therapy which seeks to make intervention more personalised.

In the context of these significant challenges, a major facilitator of the development of ACT has clearly been the wide cultural and intellectual engagement in principles of mindfulness that are so central to the approach. Recent developments in China reported by one interviewee have seen Artificial Intelligence (AI) used to 'read' a client's process in therapy and provide recommendations for the therapist (CUHK, 2023). Such deployment of AI offers a major innovation in supporting both delivery of interventions and therapist training.

In terms of lessons learned, it is very clear from the recent literature how the establishment of focused research ecosystems can prompt valuable work exploring specific lines of enquiry to inform the potential scaling of an intervention like APC (e.g. the STRENGTHS consortium working with refugees in Europe; the cluster of research studies in Iran exploring the ACT in relation to psychosis). It is also apparent – noting the over 1,000 RCTs reported in relation to ACT – that a large, heterogeneous evidence-base can present challenges for clear determination of implications for practice.

Recommendations for investment:

The above review highlights three major research gaps that would usefully be addressed:

- **Consolidating the diverse and inconsistent evidence-base to inform policy decisions on adoption.** The breadth and heterogeneity (in study design and findings) of the current evidence-base for ACT renders decision-making regarding inclusion of ACT in treatment guidelines challenging. There is a case for establishing a rigorous and authoritative 'umbrella review' (potentially exploring individual participant meta-analysis) of the effectiveness, moderators of effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of ACT for the conditions of anxiety, depression and psychosis.
- **Research on delivery formats and use of AI to accelerate scaling.** Despite the plethora of studies on ACT over the last five decades there has been comparatively little attention paid to mechanisms of scaling its use globally. Its modal use appears to remain in the consulting room in the delivery of individual therapy by those with psychological training. This is of potential value to the populations that can access such services privately or through well-financed public mental health systems. However, there remain huge opportunities to reach wider populations of persons experiencing anxiety, depression or psychosis through other modalities and other professional (and non-professional) cadres. Two key research questions are: (a) in terms of clinical impact, what formats for delivery of ACT provide the best balance between concrete, scalable protocols accessible to non-specialists (and for self-help use) and facilitating effective client engagement with the core process skills (e.g. psychological flexibility) central to the therapeutic mechanism of ACT; (b) how can AI be systematically and effectively deployed to foster quality delivery of ACT and therapist/helper supervision?

- **The need for comparative research.** The bulk of evidence regarding the effectiveness of ACT is based on comparisons with treatment as usual or waiting list controls. For efficient and appropriate decision-making, a more consistent commitment to comparative effectiveness research is required. Key comparators highlighted through this review process are CBT/DBT and IPT. Robust comparative studies between ACT and other therapeutic approaches, such as CBT and DBT, are essential to determine its relative effectiveness in different populations and clinical settings. Research investigating the neurobiological and psychological mechanisms engaged in by these alternative therapeutic approaches was also commended by some interviewees given evidence that such an understanding assists the development of effective process-based interventions (Zhao et al., 2022).

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COMMON ELEMENTS TREATMENT APPROACH (CETA)

Pipeline stage: Scale

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Member of the core team of CETA Global, Johns Hopkins School of Public Health / Applied Mental Health Research Group (AMHR)
- Certified CETA Provider from Myanmar

Target disorders:

Common Elements Treatment Approach (CETA) is a transdiagnostic approach that was originally developed for adults focusing on three common mental health problems in low and middle-income countries (LMIC): depression, post-traumatic stress, and anxiety (Murray et al., 2014).

Since then, CETA has been effectively used for the most common mental health disorders among many populations including refugee populations (Cohen & Yaeger, 2021; Murray, Hall, et al., 2018) and conflict and post-conflict settings (Ballesteros et al., 2024; Bonilla-Escobar et al., 2018; Murray, Haroz, et al., 2018) including survivors of torture (Weiss et al., 2015).

In addition, it has been proven effective in reducing interpersonal violence (Murray, Kane, et al., 2020), alcohol and substance use reduction (Kane et al., 2022), aggression (Murray, Haroz, et al., 2020), medication adherence (HIV, TB, Diabetes) (Lasater et al., 2023) and increasing safety/ reducing suicide (CETA Global, n.d.; Knettel et al., 2023).

Overview of intervention:

Common Elements Treatment Approach (CETA) diverges from the traditional linear development process seen in many interventions and has rather expanded as a multipronged system over 20 years, adapting in response to evidence gathered through ongoing implementation (CETA Global, n.d.). The developers of CETA do not conceptualise it as an intervention, but rather as a new approach to training lay counsellors (Murray, Haroz, et al., 2020). CETA's aim is the systematic implementation of common elements of evidence-based research and decision-making for treatment focus, element selection, sequencing and dosing (Murray, Haroz, et al., 2020).

Many evidence-based treatments used in LMICs are 'focal treatments', primarily targeting one disorder or mental health problem. These often face substantial barriers to scale-up and sustainability as service providers need to be trained in multiple interventions to meet the diverse and complex needs of a client population. By contrast, CETA is designed as a transdiagnostic, modularised approach that allows flexibility for the service provider to select modules based on individual client needs and clinical comorbidity. The flexibility of CETA to address multiple issues through a set of common elements in a way that allows the service provider to make personalised decisions that are tailored to individual needs is considered an effective feature of the approach (Murray, Haroz, et al., 2020). As such, both the sequencing of treatment elements, and the variance in element dose depend on the type and severity of presenting problems of the CETA participant (Nguyen et al., 2023).

There was variation in the total number of CETA elements used across the different study sites. However, CETA can be described as consisting of 8 core elements (1-8, listed below) as well as optional elements

(9-11 below) that may be introduced if relevant to context and needs. The component elements of CETA include the following: 1) encouraging participation (engagement); 2) psychoeducation; 3) relaxation (anxiety management strategies); 4) behavioural activation; 5) cognitive coping and restructuring; 6) imaginal gradual exposure; 7) in-vivo exposure; 8) safety (suicide/homicide/danger assessment and planning); 9) problem-solving (*used in Thailand*); 10) parenting skills (for caregivers only) (*used in Lebanon*); 11) screening and brief Intervention for alcohol (substance use and relapse prevention) (*used in Thailand*) (Murray et al., 2014, 2019, 2020; Pluess et al., 2024)

CETA has shown to be effective in multiple modes of implementation, including in-person and over the phone (t-CETA) (Figge et al., 2022; Pluess et al., 2024). CETA has been conducted in diverse settings, including outpatient counselling, participant homes, HIV clinics, college, community settings, and community-based hospitals (*CETA Global*, n.d.). In addition to its original form which is typically 6 – 12 sessions, a brief version of CETA comprising of 5 sessions (Brief CETA) has also been developed to be used in volatile and low-resource settings (Murray, Haroz, et al., 2018). The data and monitoring systems of CETA have been adapted to both offline as well as online triage and progress monitoring systems.

Given the breadth and depth of its use, CETA may be described as a transdiagnostic **system** of care based on cognitive behavioural therapy that provides a) a multi-problem assessment, b) a triage system, c) safety planning/suicide prevention, d) flexible treatment options from wellness and prevention through moderate and severe mental and behavioural health conditions, e) option for M&E, measurement-based care results.

Intervention development and theory of change:

The development of CETA was informed by review of evidence-based treatments and other common elements approaches by the Johns Hopkins School of Public Health, USA. CETA aimed to address two main challenges in LMIC settings. Firstly, given the lack of a skilled mental health workforce, it was required that technical materials and the training be developed using a simple, concrete format to ensure fidelity of implementation by local lay counsellors with little or no previous mental health training.

Secondly, having highly skilled professionals for decision-making and supervision is also a challenge in LMIC settings. As such CETA needed to empower supervisors and lay counsellors to (a) assess the primary focus of the issues, (b) triage and choose treatment elements and their priority order, and (c) determine the dose for each element. This flexibility given to the service providers has played a crucial role in the effectiveness of the approach. In addition, CETA also takes a multi-problem transdiagnostic approach enabling the limited workforce at the community level to be trained on a single versatile intervention capable of supporting a variety of needs as opposed to being trained on multiple evidence-based interventions which is infeasible in low resource settings due to limited funding and scarce personnel. Introducing multiple interventions to meet the needs of a single context also makes it challenging to ensure the fidelity of each intervention.

CETA, as a "system of care", comprises multiple evidence-based steps and processes. Among these are:

Implementation

CETA plays significant attention to its implementation process. In addition to being informed by implementation science research evidence on feasibility, adaptability and fidelity, the Approach also ensures that the local partners are carefully selected to be trained on CETA to ensure the sustainability of the intervention.

CETA implementation also relies on a three-tier system comprising of:

1. Trainers - who are experts in CETA but usually from outside the project area. Over the years CETA Global has created a repository of regional certified trainers for the approach.
2. Supervisors - who are ideally local individuals who have been chosen for a more advanced role.
3. Counsellors - local individuals who actually conduct the CETA sessions with the clients. (Murray et al., 2011, p. 3)

Assessment

CETA uses a multi-problem Client Monitoring Form to assess, refer, and monitor improvement. The online CETA system is designed to triage individuals or groups to different levels of care, from prevention/wellness all the way through treatment and maintenance.

Training

Training methodologies for CETA personnel include in-person, via technology or in hybrid by certified trainers.

Treatment

The typical CETA intervention would last between 6 – 12 sessions depending on the client's need. However, a shorter version of the intervention “Brief CETA / CETA psychosocial support (CPSS)” has also been developed for contexts where longer-term engagement may not be practical.

CETA session can be carried out individually and/or in groups on a weekly (or bi-weekly) basis either in-person or remotely depending on their level of need (i.e., precision-based care). A session is designed to last for about 20-60+ minutes.

Monitoring and Evaluation

CETA trained counsellors receive weekly supervision by local supervisors, who receive guidance from certified trainers. The global pool of trainers in turn receives guidance from the global CETA network. CETA collects data on the client’s progress every step of the way mainly regarding triage, prioritisation of issues and dosage. The approach is adaptable to recording the data in online system (*CETA Care Confidence*, n.d.) or offline paper-based systems based on context. CETA includes a “Client Monitoring Form” that assesses, triages, and monitors a client’s problems and improvement. This is a short, practical (5-10 minute) assessment.

Efficacy and effectiveness:

There is no published systematic review for CETA, and its evidence-base is informed by 8 Randomized Control Trials (RCTs) to evaluate the effectiveness of the approach (*CETA Global*, n.d.), carried out across different settings providing evidence of the appropriateness, applicability and adoption of the approach in diverse contexts (mainly LMICs). Overall, CETA has shown strong effect sizes in addressing depression and moderate to strong effect sizes for anxiety across multiple contexts. CETA is not considered an appropriate intervention for psychosis (Pluess et al., 2024). Given the transdiagnostic nature of the intervention, the evidence related to the target conditions of depression and anxiety are described below for each trial.

RCTs conducted in Thailand with adult Burmese refugees showing decreased post-traumatic stress, depression, and dysfunction (Bolton et al., 2014). The single blinded study compared CETA (n = 182) with wait-list control (WLC) (n = 165). CETA participants experienced significantly greater reductions of baseline symptoms across all measured outcomes – depression and PTS (primary outcomes) and functional impairment, anxiety symptoms, aggression, and alcohol use (secondary outcomes) - with the exception of alcohol use (alcohol use analysis was confined to problem drinkers).

The difference in mean change from pre-intervention to post-intervention between intervention and control groups was 20.49 (95% CI: 20.59, 20.40) for depression, 20.43 (95% CI: 20.51, 20.35) for PTS, 20.42 (95% CI: 20.58, 20.27) for functional impairment, 20.48 (95% CI: 20.61, 20.34) for anxiety, 20.24 (95% CI: 20.34, 20.15) for aggression, and 20.03 (95% CI: 20.44, 0.50) for alcohol use.

This corresponded to a 77% reduction in mean baseline depression score among CETA participants compared to a 40% reduction among controls, with respective values for the other outcomes of 76% and 41% for anxiety, 75% and 37% for PTS, 67% and 22% for functional impairment, and 71% and 32% for aggression. Effect sizes (Cohen's *d*) were large for depression ($d = 1.16$) and PTS ($d = 1.19$); moderate for impaired function ($d = 0.63$), anxiety ($d = 0.79$), and aggression ($d = 0.58$); and none for alcohol use.

Trials in Iraq with adults exposed to systematic violence showing reduced PTSD (Weiss et al., 2015). This randomized, parallel, two site, two-arm (1:1 allocation), single-blinded, wait-list controlled (WLC) trial of CETA in one site (99 CETA, 50 WLC), and cognitive processing therapy (CPT) in a second site (129 CPT, 64 WLC) showed large effect size for CETA across all outcomes (trauma symptoms (Cohen's *d*) (effect size = 1.5), depression effect size = 1.3 and anxiety symptoms - effect size = 1.1).

Trials in Zambia among adults (couples with one child in the house) focused on reducing substance use and IPV. It also showed a reduction in depression, post-traumatic stress, and anxiety which were secondary outcomes. (Murray, Kane, et al., 2020). The single-blind, parallel-assignment RCT compared the effects of CETA ($n=123$ couples) to Treatment as usual with safety checks ($n=125$).

CETA was also used in Zambia among adults affected by HIV and alcohol to reduce the unhealthy alcohol use (Kane et al., 2022). While CETA was compared with single-session alcohol brief intervention (BI) alone or BI plus referral to CETA where BI plus CETA showed significant alcohol reduction on the AUDIT scores compared to BI alone ($- 3.2$, 95% CI $- 6.2$ to $- 0.1$; Cohen's *d*: 0.48). CETA treatment effects were observed for depression as secondary outcomes where the BI plus CETA group also experienced statistically significantly greater reductions in depression ($- 4.2$, 95% CI $- 8.9$ to $- 0.5$, $d = 0.5$) and trauma symptoms ($- 0.2$, 95% CI $- 0.5$ to $- 0.1$, $d = 0.38$) compared to the BI alone group.

RCT with children from Ethiopia and Somali in refugee camps showed reduced internalising, externalising, and posttraumatic stress symptoms and improved well-being (Murray, Hall, et al., 2018). Children who participated in the CETA-Youth open trial ($N=37$) reported significant decreases in symptoms of internalising ($d = 1.37$), externalising ($d = 0.85$), and posttraumatic stress ($d = 1.71$), and improvements in well-being ($d = 0.75$). Caregivers also reported significant decreases in child symptoms. Depression and anxiety related data were not collected as part of the trial.

In a scoping review of health promotion interventions for victims of Colombian armed conflict, CETA showed reductions in PTSD (-0.23 ; $P=0.02$) and depression symptoms ($- 0.23$; $P= 0.02$), along with improved function (Ballesteros et al., 2024).

A unique RCT was carried out in Ukraine to compare the effectiveness of the full CETA and Brief CETA interventions among veterans and IDP communities (Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, 2019; Murray, Haroz, et al., 2018). While depression, PTSD and anxiety were considered as outcome evaluation measures the results of the trial have not yet been published.

Trajectories of change show steady symptom decline over time (Murray, Haroz, et al., 2020). Findings suggest that modular, flexible transdiagnostic models may allow for more efficient, targeted treatment as more insights are gained about key ingredients, their timing within treatment, and client outcomes (Murray, Haroz, et al., 2020).

Relevance to PLE:

CETA relies on persons with lived experience to be a part of their contextual adaptation (translation and cultural adaptation) process in new settings. The local adaptation is handled by a local partner who engages with PLE as part of the process (Interview - A). In some contexts, implementing partners for CETA have staff who are members of the affected population groups (i.e., torture survivors or survivors of intimate partner violence), and an interviewee also indicated that this was true for some certified CETA providers in the global trainer pool.

The main components of the intervention are designed at the Johns Hopkins School of Public Health / CETA Global based on the evidence generated from the field. There is no apparent role for PLE involvement in this process to date.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

CETA has a clearly defined process of implementation. This includes guidance on the selection of local partners, translation and adaptation of materials, setting up the 3 layers of professionals, training, community implementation and monitoring. Each step is articulated in detail within the approach.

One of the main components of the resource materials is the training material for counsellors and supervisors. Each CETA component is designed in a 1–5 page “manual” section and a 1–2 page “steps sheet.” The steps sheets include both goals and example wording for many goals, to provide extra guidance for lay counsellors. Steps sheets are designed for use when practising and preparing for sessions and also during sessions to help navigate the module.

CETA counsellors and supervisors are provided with a 2-week training by a Certified CETA trainer using an apprenticeship model (Murray et al., 2014). Certified CETA trainers are trained and accredited by CETA Global. The training cascade linked to CETA Global system has resource implications for implementing the CETA approach, and costs may vary by context.

CETA implementation also requires weekly supervision meetings for counsellors and supervisors. Given the high contact hours, materials (online and offline), and number of required personnel, CETA is likely more cost and resource-intensive than many focal treatments (i.e. PM+, Thinking Healthy) to implement. However, given that CETA is designed to address multiple problems, this could potentially make it more cost-effective than training staff on multiple interventions, although no comparative studies or data were found. CETA may also reduce the need for referral and may provide more efficient care to the client. As indicated by an interviewee, if the local online access are sufficient, the use of the online system can make the intervention more cost effective.

Shorter versions of CETA (Brief CETA – 5 sessions and CPSS – 6 sessions) have been introduced as less cost and resource intensive versions compared to the original 6-12 session CETA.

Context, applicability and scalability:

CETA has been used successfully with many populations including, populations exposed to violent traumatic events, refugees and displaced adults, men and women with interpersonal violence and using substances, health workers, people living with HIV/Diabetes and other physical health issues, perinatal women and their family members, and communities in LMIC and HIC settings. Currently, CETA has been implemented in almost 20 countries across all 6 WHO regions.

All these implementations are managed and facilitated through CETA Global the multidisciplinary team at the Johns Hopkins School of Public Health. While resource materials are publicly available/requestable, any field implementation and training of counsellors for CETA can only be done by Certified CETA trainers

affiliated with the CETA Global team. Based on interviews with CETA creators, this measure has been put in place to ensure the safety of the vulnerable populations that CETA caters to especially due to its potential to work with trauma exposure and suicidality. They identify that ensuring fidelity of the module implementation and supervisory mechanism is paramount to the approach.

While CETA as an approach can be widely applied to diverse contexts with well-documented benefits, its scalability requires adequate preparation and resourcing at the ground level for establishment and sustainability.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

CETA presents a model of service delivery that aims to set a supervised care system at the community level through an intervention package that is able to address multiple problems and comorbidities. It also provides the flexibility to engage at an individual or group level as well as tailor the module sequencing individual needs and priorities. The adherence to fidelity and progress monitoring also aims to safeguard clients from further harm due to poorly implemented initiatives. However, such rigidity in implementation may also be viewed as being over-prescriptive and overly uniform (Edwards, 2020).

CETA also aims to empower local personnel and organisations to carry this initiative forward beyond the initial training and evaluation phase by CETA Global. However, given the resource intensiveness of the interventions (financial, personnel, time), both interviewees noted that some settings find it difficult to continue the approach in the longer term. This was mainly due to competing priorities with other programmes implemented by local partners, the extensive documentation and data collection requirements, the care burden, and the loss of trained personnel for supervision.

The success of CETA was largely seen as dependent on the commitment of the counsellors and supervisors to implement, and it is important that they are placed and supported within a robust service delivery system within which CETA is embedded.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

CETA is an intervention on which there has been significant investment in evidence generation. Backed and governed by a prestigious academic institution, it has established a strong evidence base for its effectiveness across many contexts, populations, and comorbidities.

The fact that CETA is a modular, flexible, multi-problem transdiagnostic treatment has facilitated and enhanced its adaptability (Murray et al., 2014). CETA also works with 11 elements, therefore, unlike interventions that work with a larger number of elements (i.e. mhGAP), training laypeople can be more focussed. Furthermore, CETA has further adapted to create brief versions of the intervention (Brief CETA, CPSS) to increase its usage.

The extensive system set up by CETA Global ensures that the implementation of the approach including the training of counsellors and sessions with the clients are carried out in a robust manner. However, the system that CETA gets embedded in plays a crucial role in its sustainability. Since the CETA implementation model requires 3 levels of personnel (counsellors, supervisors, and certified CETA trainers), sustaining that model requires considerable buy-in and resources. Ideally, the CETA process should be embedded within a service-providing institution's core service-delivery processes. With competing priorities for organisations in low-resource settings, obtaining buy-in and effecting this this may pose a barrier to uptake and sustainability.

The online system of CETA poses many advantages including providing tailored technical input for clients, however, this may not be a possibility in low-resource vulnerable settings where the internet access is limited or not financially supported.

For settings where there is an adequate availability of existing psychologists, CBT therapists or other licensed practitioners, CETA may appear to be too basic or may not meet required professional standards. However, in contexts where access to such human resources are scarce and task-sharing to lay counsellors is indicated, CETA presents a credible means to addressing the treatment gap.

Recommendations for investment:

CETA is an intervention in the advanced stages of the implementation pipeline. It has been studied and implemented in many contexts. The following are research-related recommendations for potential future investment.

Research Recommendations

- **Study the sustainability of CETA implementation beyond trial or project funded periods.** Much of the evidence generated on CETA stems from randomised controlled trials aimed at measuring the efficacy of the approach in a given context. moving forward it would benefit to look into the sustainability of CETA beyond the trial or experimental period. As such investing in post-study hybrid type 3 implementation studies would provide more insights on challenges and supportive factors to sustain CETA in the communities.
- **Study factors that support CETA integration within diverse contexts.** Given that CETA is seen as a system rather than an intervention, the ability for the approach to be sustainably implemented in a given context requires adoption and integration by supportive systems. It would be beneficial to study the factors that support or hinder this process.
- **Study impact of CETA delivered together with other social interventions.** Given that the vulnerabilities of populations CETA is being used with are related to social determinants of mental health (i.e.. losses, insecurity, violence and poverty) linking to other forms of assistance (i.e. access to social protection, livelihoods, housing, vocational training). to be delivered in conjunction with CETA might be a productive area to explore to further amplify the impact of the approach.

Ecosystem Recommendations

- **Explore lower-cost alternatives to the existing supervisory model.** Maintaining the 3-tier supervisory model can pose a significant recourse burden to implementing partners, especially to sustain adequate financing for this. Scaling CETA may require exploring less resource intensive methodologies.

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EYE MOVEMENT DESENSITISATION AND REPROCESSING THERAPY (EMDR)

Pipeline stage: Scale

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Medical Doctor, EMDR trainer and founder of an EMDR training Institute in Europe. Training facilitator, certified therapist by EMDRIA, and an adjunct faculty for the Trauma Counselling Programme at a University in the USA
- Researcher and licensed therapist at an EMDR Association
- Mental health professional and lived experience expert

Target disorders:

Eye Movement Desensitisation and Reprocessing (EMDR) is an empirically supported intervention for trauma-related conditions, with systematic reviews and meta-analyses highlighting its efficacy across post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety disorders, depression, and psychosis, though evidence quality and applicability vary by condition (Shapiro, 1989; Cujipers et al., 2020).

Overview of intervention:

EMDR is a structured, eight-phase psychotherapy initially developed to treat post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) by facilitating the reprocessing of unprocessed traumatic memories (Shapiro, 1989). Unlike exposure-based therapies, EMDR uses bilateral stimulation (e.g., guided eye movements, tactile taps, or auditory tones) to help clients process these memories while maintaining dual attention to past and present experiences.

The intervention's standardised protocol enables – rooted in the Adaptive Information Processing (AIP) model – delivery across diverse settings, including outpatient clinics, telehealth platforms, and humanitarian contexts. Key components include:

1. History-Taking and Treatment Planning: Identifying target memories and associated beliefs.
2. Preparation: Establishing coping strategies for emotional regulation.
3. Assessment: Evaluating the vividness of traumatic memories and maladaptive beliefs.
4. Desensitisation: Using bilateral stimulation to reduce emotional distress.
5. Installation: Reinforcing adaptive beliefs (e.g., "I am safe now").
6. Body Scan: Addressing residual physical sensations linked to trauma.
7. Closure: Stabilising the client post-session.
8. Re-evaluation: Reviewing progress in subsequent sessions.

EMDR's structured yet flexible framework allows adaptations for comorbid conditions (e.g., depression, anxiety) and populations, including children and culturally diverse groups. Systematic reviews note its advantage over trauma-focused cognitive-behavioural therapy (TF-CBT) in requiring less homework and explicit exposure, which may reduce dropout rates (Wright et al., 2024). While emerging evidence supports its use for anxiety disorders, trauma-related depression, and psychosis, though, methodological limitations (e.g., small samples, reliance on self-reports) and a lack of long-term data weaken confidence in its broader applicability.

Intervention development and theory of change:

The development of EMDR therapy was stimulated by a direct personal observation by its founder Francine Shapiro in the late 1980s, rather than an existing theoretical treatment paradigm. The evolution of EMDR therapy has, however been informed and shaped by other existing approaches and theories over its progression from (a) a simple technique (eye movements), to (b) an initial procedure (EMD), to (c) a protocol (EMDR) for treatment of one condition (PTSD), and to (d) an overall approach to therapy that is well-established and widely used internationally (Leeds, 2009).

The therapy's guiding framework, the Adaptive Information Processing (AIP) model, holds that once maladaptive memories are appropriately reprocessed, the intensity of associated emotions, beliefs, and physical sensations diminishes. The AIP model guides and supports the management of cases from conceptualisation, treatment planning, resolving clinical impasses, and anticipating clinical outcomes.

EMDR's eight-phase protocol - which spans history-taking through re-evaluation - seeks to facilitate this reprocessing using bilateral stimulation (e.g., eye movements, tactile taps) while preserving a dual focus on both the targeted memory and present safety cues. Unlike exposure-based models, EMDR typically involves less explicit discussion of traumatic events, a difference which may improve tolerability and reduce dropout in certain populations (Wright et al., 2024). EMDR's subcortical mechanisms, which do not hinge on extensive verbal processing, make it particularly applicable to children or clients averse to detailed recollection of distressing experiences. The theory of change posits that, as reprocessing modifies the stored memory's affective intensity and content, individuals experience reduced symptoms and adopt more adaptive beliefs (e.g., shifting from "I am unsafe" to "I have overcome this"). This core mechanism underlies EMDR's extension from post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) to a broader range of conditions, including anxiety and depression, where unresolved or inadequately processed experiences may contribute to ongoing distress (Carletto et al., 2021).

According to the EMDR International Association, professionals have to complete a Basic EMDR Training that is approved by the EMDR International Association to be considered an EMDR trained clinician. Whilst EMDRIA indicates minimal eligibility requirements for Basic EMDR training for mental health professionals (ie. medical doctors, nurses and other mental health practitioners such as psychologists, counsellors, clinical social workers) and graduate trainees, different national or sub-national jurisdictions may have their own requirements for EMDR training. For example, there are regional EMDR associations (ie. EMDR ASIA) which also approve EMDR trainings conducted at country-level by affiliated national associations.

The **EMDR Global Alliance (EGA)** outlines the **Minimum Training Standards for EMDR Therapy (2024)**. Its purpose is to establish universal guidelines that ensure consistent, high-quality EMDR education and effective mental health services globally.

Key elements include:

- 1. Global Standards:** The EGA has set minimum international guidelines for training EMDR practitioners, consultants, and trainers, agreed upon by its member regional associations.
- 2. Eligibility for Training:** Participants must meet the licensing or professional requirements for mental health practice in their country. In regions without a licensing system, eligibility will be determined by the national or regional association.
Trainer Requirements: Trainers must hold qualifications in mental health, be licensed in their country, and be accredited by their national or regional EMDR association. They must follow a curriculum based on Dr. Francine Shapiro's principles and encourage ongoing professional development.

3. **Training Structure:** The basic EMDR training includes 20 hours of lectures, 18 hours of supervised practice, and 10 hours of consultation, spanning at least six days. The training may be divided into multiple parts, with consultation spread out to ensure integration of EMDR techniques into clinical practice.
4. **Certification & Accreditation:** To become a Certified or Accredited EMDR Practitioner, individuals must complete an approved basic training, have two years of professional experience, conduct at least 50 EMDR sessions, and complete 10 hours of additional consultation. Certification must be renewed every five years, including continued education.
5. **Consultation/Supervision:** Trainees must undergo 10 hours of consultation or supervision with an accredited consultant to ensure they are developing their skills and adhering to ethical standards in practice.
6. **Advanced Training:** Only those who have completed accredited basic EMDR training are eligible for advanced EMDR courses.

EGA indicates that its guidelines are designed to guarantee that EMDR therapy is practiced consistently and with professionalism, maintaining high standards globally (EMDR Global Alliance, n.d.).

An EMDRIA interviewee highlighted the fact that EMDR is now widely supported by international treatment guidelines, including:

- [Australian Guidelines for PTSD \(2024\)](#)
- [World Health Organization \(2023\)](#)
- [Department of Veterans Affairs & Department of Defense \(2023\)](#)
- [International Society for Traumatic Stress Studies \(2019\)](#)
- [National Institute for Health and Care Excellence \(2018\)](#)
- [American Psychological Association \(2017\)](#)
- [World Health Organization and UNHCR \(2015, 2013\)](#)
- [The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews \(2013\)](#)
- [United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees \(2013\)](#)
- [Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services America \(2014\)](#)

The exact mechanisms behind how EMDR works are unclear and have sparked ongoing debate for years (Cujipers *et al*, 2020). Some researchers believe that EMDR's effectiveness is due to the cognitive-behavioural components it incorporates, particularly exposure to traumatic memories, while arguing that the eye movements themselves do not significantly contribute to the improvement of patients, but more recent meta-analyses of dismantling studies—where EMDR was compared with the same procedure without the eye movements—suggest that the eye movements may, in fact, play a role and contribute to EMDR's effects (Cujipers *et al*, 2020).

There is considerable theoretical and experimental research on the mechanisms underlying EMDR, with two primary models receiving the most attention and support. The first model proposes that EMDR triggers an orienting response, where the eye movements activate an “investigatory reflex” that causes an alert response, followed by a sense of relaxation when no threat is perceived, which helps to reduce the negative emotions related to the traumatic memory. By increasing alertness and encouraging exploratory behaviour, the activation of this reflex also makes cognitive processes more flexible and efficient (Cujipers *et al*, 2020).

The second well-supported model states that when a traumatic memory is brought into working memory while the patient simultaneously concentrates on the movement of the fingers, the vividness and emotional

intensity of the memory are diminished. This “blurred” memory is then stored in long-term memory, resulting in a less emotional response when it is later activated. Studies have found that other dual-task activities, such as mental arithmetic, can produce similar effects (Cuijpers *et al*, 2020).

Efficacy and effectiveness:

EMDR is a scalable, evidence-based intervention with the strongest empirical support for post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), demonstrating large effect sizes compared to waitlist controls and equivalence to trauma-focused cognitive-behavioural therapy (TF-CBT) in symptom reduction (Wright *et al.*, 2024). For instance, Wright *et al.* (2024) included eight studies (totalling 346 participants) from Iran (1), the Netherlands (1), Australia (3), Italy (2), and Scotland (1) in their analysis, further illustrating EMDR’s global reach. Its application extends to anxiety disorders, trauma-related depression, and psychosis, though evidence quality varies, with smaller effect sizes and methodological limitations in non-PTSD populations (Cuijpers *et al.*, 2020; Carletto *et al.*, 2021). In particular, the systematic review and meta-analysis by Cuijpers *et al.* (2020) drew on 77 studies from diverse settings – including the USA (38), the Netherlands (11), Turkey (2), Italy (2), Iran (5), Israel (1), Taiwan (1), France (2), Germany (2), Sweden (1), Pakistan (1), Spain (1), Canada (1), the UK (1), Mexico (2), South Korea (1), and Australia (3) – showcasing the broad range of countries involved in EMDR research.

PTSD

EMDR for PTSD has shown large effect sizes when compared to wait-list control groups, although the specific additional benefits of this intervention remain uncertain, but has shown smaller effects when compared to treatment-as-usual and other active treatments such as CBT (Wright *et al*, 2024). However, no significant differences were found between EMDR and other psychological treatments such as trauma-focused CBT regarding PTSD severity, treatment response and dropout rates (Wright *et al*, 2024).

For PTSD, specifically, EMDR demonstrated a large effect size compared to control conditions ($g = 0.93$; 95% CI: 0.67–1.18), and indications of publication bias were present in studies. After adjusting for missing studies, the effect size decreased to $g = 0.76$ (95% CI: 0.49–1.04). EMDR was also found to be more effective than other therapies ($g = 0.36$; 95% CI: 0.14–0.57), but this advantage disappeared in studies with a low risk of bias ($g = 0.07$; 95% CI: –0.10 to 0.23) (Cuijpers *et al*, 2020).

Depression

When compared to inactive control groups such as waitlist or no intervention, EMDR was found to be viable and effective in reducing depressive symptoms, and, in regards to active interventions, it has demonstrated to have more effective results than psychoeducation and comparable results to CBT (Carletto *et al*, 2017; Carletto *et al*, 2021). However, studies on this topic are often found to be heavily influenced by methodological flaws, including small sample sizes, high risk of bias and significant variability, and to have its outcomes assessed through self-reported measures, all of which may lead to an overestimation of the effectiveness of EMDR (Carletto *et al*, 2017; Carletto *et al*, 2021; Dominguez *et al*, 2021). For instance, Carletto *et al.* (2017) reviewed 7 studies – 4 from Asia (China, Iran, Pakistan, and Taiwan), 2 from Germany, and 1 from North America – across which a total of 148 participants received EMDR and 146 served as controls (with study sample sizes ranging from just 26 to 64). Additionally, there is a lack of studies on the effectiveness of the intervention for depression evaluating the treatment in a double-blind condition (Carletto *et al*, 2017) and assessing the long-term effects of EMDR on the condition (Carletto *et al*, 2021). Carletto *et al.* (2021) included 11 studies for qualitative synthesis and 9 in a meta-analysis (totalling 373 participants). Dominguez *et al.* (2016) similarly reviewed 11 studies ($N = 567$), covering participants from Iran (2), Australia, Pakistan, Germany (2), the USA (2), Taiwan, Spain, and Italy.

According to Seok & Kim, 2024, evidence on the efficacy of EMDR in treating depression demonstrated a significant effect in reducing symptoms, with a Hedges' g of 0.75 (95% CI: 0.54–0.97). Meta-regression analysis revealed that depression severity significantly influenced EMDR's effectiveness ($p = 0.007$), with greater benefits observed in individuals with severe depression. Subgroup analysis indicated that the effect size varied by the number of sessions: Hedges' $g = 0.62$ (95% CI: 0.42–0.82) for five or fewer sessions, 0.44 (95% CI: 0.03–0.84) for six to ten sessions, and 1.13 (95% CI: 0.72–1.54) for more than 11 sessions. Additionally, EMDR was more effective for moderate-to-severe depression (Hedges' $g = 0.99$, 95% CI: 0.71–1.26) compared to mild depression (Hedges' $g = 0.46$, 95% CI: 0.21–0.71). The conclusions highlight that EMDR is an effective non-pharmacological intervention for depression, particularly in severe cases, though the need for more standardised research and long-term studies to assess its sustained impact is emphasised (Seok & Kim, 2024). In this meta-analysis, 25 studies were examined: 3 focused on children and adolescents, while the remainder involved adults. Sample sizes ranged from 17 to 83, with a total of 522 participants in EMDR groups and 520 in control groups.

Anxiety

In treating anxiety, EMDR showed a moderate, statistically significant effect at post-treatment ($g = 0.53$, $p = .003$), but no significant effect was observed at maintenance ($g = -0.11$, $p = .69$). Key factors influencing effect sizes included intervention duration, number of sessions, therapist experience, and therapist type. Notably, studies with a lower methodological quality (Jadad score of 3) reported larger post-treatment effect sizes for anxiety symptoms ($g = 0.79$, $p = .0002$) compared to studies with higher methodological quality. EMDR significantly outperformed wait-list control or non-active treatment in addressing anxious ($g = 0.61$, $p = .03$) symptoms, but was not superior to active treatments. Additionally, studies published before 2007 showed significantly larger effect sizes than more recent publications. Meta-regression analysis indicated that treatment duration and sample size were positively associated with effect size (Rasines-Laudes & Serrano-Pintado, 2023).

EMDR was found to be efficacious for reducing symptoms of anxiety, panic, phobia, and behavioural/somatic symptoms (Yunitri *et al*, 2020). However, it was also observed that whilst EMDR show efficacy in treating phobias and test anxiety, for other anxiety disorders and comparators there are insufficient studies to calculate combined effect sizes, and very few studies have a low risk of bias, which leaves the findings on efficacy inconclusive in relation to these conditions (Cujipers *et al*, 2020). Staton *et al*. (2022), examined 28 studies, with 13 in Europe, 7 in North America, 1 in South America, 3 in Australia, and 4 in Asia, reflecting EMDR's growing use in anxiety treatment worldwide.

Psychosis

Emerging evidence supports EMDR's role in psychosis, with preliminary studies linking it to reduced delusional conviction and hospital readmission rates; however, mixed results on auditory hallucinations and paranoid thinking underscore the need for further validation (Adams *et al.*, 2020). Adams *et al.* (2020) included 236 adult participants (106 receiving EMDR and 130 controls), with sample sizes ranging from 27 to 155 across multiple trials. An interviewee, who is a medical doctor and EMDR trainer, stated that for psychosis, specifically, when someone is actively experiencing a psychotic episode or is in the midst of a psychotic disorder, EMDR reprocessing is not suitable, but it may become effective once the person is stabilised with medication.

Various Conditions

According to an interviewee associated with EMDR International Association, EMDR is beneficial for a wide range of issues, including somatic problems, grief, addictions, dissociation, and more, it is used worldwide and was proven effective across various populations and conditions.

Reviewed evidence shows that EMDR has been assessed across a diverse range of samples, including different ages, medically unexplained conditions, psychological comorbidities, and cultural backgrounds, which suggests that it may be used with various populations (Staton *et al*, 2022). However, a systematic review and meta-analysis that explored efficacy in treating a range of mental health conditions in addition to PTSD, such as depression, eating disorders, alcoholism, pain, schizophrenia, OCD, bipolar disorder, and conduct disorder, found that there were not enough studies in these areas to conduct a pooled analysis and the risk of bias was high in many studies (Cujipers *et al*, 2020). Therefore, the researchers concluded the existing evidence to be insufficient to support the use of EMDR for mental health issues beyond PTSD.

While EMDR's structured protocol enables broad applicability, its evidence base remains strongest for PTSD, with other conditions requiring larger, more rigorous trials to establish clinical utility.

Relevance to PLE:

While the core EMDR protocol is standardised, co-designing adaptations with PLE can bolster cultural and linguistic relevance - especially in humanitarian or cross-cultural settings, where local idioms of distress and communal practices can inform bilateral stimulation approaches. PLE feedback may also clarify strategies for session pacing, safety planning, and after-session support, ensuring that interventions align with family systems, resource limitations, and community norms.

An interviewed stakeholder shared their perspective on EMDR therapy, particularly focusing on the accessibility and demographic factors. They noted that their exposure to EMDR has mainly been through people aged 18 to 28, who are aware of and have access to the therapy. While they have heard positive feedback about EMDR, they emphasise that those providing the feedback tend to come from more privileged backgrounds, raising concerns about the broader accessibility of this intervention, *"In the Indian context, I think that EMDR , as an intervention, is quite expensive, and the therapy sessions are usually more expensive than, let's say, talk therapy sessions or any other sort of therapy sessions."*

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

EMDR was found to be the most cost-effective treatment for adults with PTSD with symptoms showing more than three months after trauma in comparison with somatic/cognitive therapies, supported self-help, psychoeducation, Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors, Trauma-focused CBT, unsupported self-help, non TF-CBT, TF-CBT + SSRIs and counselling (Mavranezouli *et al*, 2020).

Cost-effectiveness analyses favour EMDR for chronic PTSD due to lower relapse rates and reduced long-term healthcare costs compared to pharmacotherapy (Mavranezouli *et al.*, 2020).

Context, applicability and scalability:

The intervention's structured protocol enables delivery across outpatient, telehealth, and humanitarian settings, with task-sharing models allowing non-specialists to administer EMDR under supervision, though fidelity challenges persist in low-resource contexts (Staton *et al.*, 2022).

Cultural adaptations, such as integrating local metaphors for trauma or collaborative goal-setting with clients, are increasingly emphasised to enhance engagement in non-Western contexts, though evidence for these modifications remains nascent.

According to the interviewees, the cultural adaptation of EMDR is easy as it is not a talking therapy. However, adaptations might be necessary for different cultural groups or specific conditions, requiring adjustments to the protocols used.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

EMDR's potential to reduce mental health disparities is limited by systemic inequities, including cultural mismatches (e.g., Eurocentric trauma narratives alienating non-Western explanatory models), geographic scarcity of multilingual providers, and financial barriers to EMDR certification in low-resource settings. Marginalised populations – such as refugees, incarcerated individuals, and racial/ethnic minorities – often face distrust in institutionalised care and prioritisation of survival needs over therapy. Therefore, EMDR therapy's ability to follow the task-sharing model (training community health workers) and to make culturally informed adaptations (e.g. integration of spiritual practices) holds promise, especially for these populations, but requires rigorous evaluation and PLE-led advocacy to address structural biases.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

Barriers:

A persistent challenge in the field is that meta-analyses frequently highlight that RCTs have insufficient statistical power to identify significant moderators and predictors of treatment effects for EMDR. This is a key gap since the understanding of potential moderators and predictors of the effectiveness of the intervention could lead to a more precise identification of the individuals who would benefit from the therapy (Wright et al, 2024). According to one interviewee, another important barrier is that clinicians are often sceptical about the therapy and how it works, suggesting that more research on how EMDR works is needed to build trust in the intervention. Another interviewee shared that the application of EMDR becomes increasingly complex when working with clients facing greater challenges and vulnerabilities. Finally, one interviewee noted that, over the past two decades, EMDR has been extensively adapted to accommodate a wide range of global cultures. A key point of debate has resulted around the concept of task-sharing. While EMDR lends itself well to this practice, countries take different views on the professional background required to allow individuals to become EMDR therapists (e.g. some countries consider that only professionals with a mental health background may become EMDR therapists, while other countries consider that professionals with a social or healthcare background such as social workers, medical doctors and nurses may apply the therapy as well). The interviewee indicated that ongoing research and development efforts are actively addressing these challenges.

Facilitators:

An interviewee shared that the typical model for delivering EMDR training is relatively brief, usually spanning 6 to 7 days. The therapy, as an eight-phase treatment, has a fundamental simplicity. EMDR, therefore, is considered to be highly structured and simple to administer, and involves less exposure to imaginal trauma/distressing memory when compared to other trauma-focused therapies such as TF-CBT (Wright et al, 2024).

Recommendations for investment:

Research Recommendations

- **Expand the Evidence Base to Understudied and Complex Populations:** While EMDR's efficacy is well-documented for standard PTSD, there is a pressing need to investigate its applications for *complex PTSD* and severe comorbidities, where relapse rates tend to be higher and additional sessions may be required. Expanded funding should focus on larger, multi-session trials and longitudinal designs that can account for reemergence of symptoms and complex clinical presentations. According to an interviewee, the academic literature on EMDR supports certain aspects of the approach, though there are areas where it is less conclusive. A primary criticism of much of the research is its focus on effectiveness, often neglecting to consider broader social, environmental, and community factors. Donors, on the other hand, tend to prioritise funding initiatives that address these

wider issues. The interviewee states that exploring the use of EMDR with broader metrics, such as reducing gender-based violence, enhancing community recovery and engagement, decreasing family violence, and improving student engagement in schools, could make EMDR more attractive to donors.

- **Strengthen Implementation and Cost-Effectiveness Analyses:** Existing evidence points to EMDR's cost-effectiveness for chronic PTSD (Mavranouzouli et al., 2020), yet more nuanced analyses are needed for populations requiring extended care (e.g., complex PTSD). Research should examine how **increased session frequency** or specialised protocols impact both treatment outcomes and healthcare costs. Implementation trials that incorporate **task-sharing** to trained non-specialists and **telehealth formats** can broaden EMDR's reach in low-resource or conflict-affected settings. Tracking relapse rates, dropout, and fidelity in these contexts will inform scalable, resource-efficient models of care.
- **Refine Protocols for Complex Trauma and Comorbidities:** Complex PTSD and other severe presentations often involve multiple traumatic events, dissociative symptoms, and fluctuating stability. Investments should support the development and testing of *adapted EMDR protocols* tailored to complex cases. Research on phased treatment approaches (e.g., incorporating stabilisation techniques before intensive EMDR) could clarify how best to sequence interventions to minimise re-traumatisation and reduce dropout in complex populations.
- **Integrate Mechanism and Process Research:** Advanced studies focusing on **mechanisms** (e.g., memory reconsolidation, bilateral stimulation) and **process variables** (e.g., session pacing, therapist-client rapport) can guide refinement of EMDR protocols for more severe disorders. Including **qualitative measures** – such as interviews or feedback from persons with lived experience – would enrich understanding of how and why EMDR works or fails in challenging clinical cases.

Ecosystem Recommendations

- **Ensure High-Quality Training and Supervision:** The interviewees emphasise that **therapist competence** strongly affects outcomes. Investment in EMDR training programmes, can foster higher fidelity in both research and routine practice. Ongoing supervision, peer consultation, and refresher workshops should be central to funding models, ensuring that skill levels are maintained over time. Research assessing *therapist qualifications* and supervision quality would allow better control of potential confounding factors in clinical trials. Additionally, an interviewee stated that task-sharing in EMDR is particularly crucial in environments where the demand for services exceeds supply and existing mental health systems are insufficient.

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INTERPERSONAL PSYCHOTHERAPY (IPT)

Pipeline stage: Scale

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Associate Professor of Clinical Psychology and Global Health Director, USA
- Associate Professor of Clinical Psychology and Director, Global Health Lab, Teachers College, Columbia University, New York, NY, USA
- Emeritus Professor of Psychiatry and Psychology and former Chair of the International Institute for Interpersonal Psychotherapy, USA
- IPT Clinician and Researcher, Federal University of São Paulo, Brazil Psychiatrist, Provincial Health Directorate of Sofala Mozambique

Target disorders:

Originally developed to address depression but is increasingly being deployed with respect to other disorders including anxiety and PTSD. Some potential for wider transdiagnostic use, particularly in relation to interpersonal issues relevant to the aetiology, maintenance or management of other conditions.

Scope:

With potential for application across a diverse range of cultural contexts, the focus of this review is to identify gaps in current knowledge that, if addressed, could promote a shift towards widescale adoption.

Overview of intervention:

IPT is a manualised, time-limited intervention typically delivered over 12-16 sessions where the focus - over three phases of treatment - is on linking mood and emotion to (challenges in) interpersonal relationships (logged in an Inventory of Interpersonal Problems). Group IPT (IPT-G) is the form of the intervention most widely used for delivery by non-specialists, guided by a manual co-developed with the WHO for use in relation to the mhGAP initiative (WHO and Columbia University, 2016). A brief format of the intervention – Interpersonal Counselling (IPC) – particularly one delivered over just three sessions – IPC-3 – is the most recent focus of scale-up. IPT delivered in these varying formats is at the pipeline stage of ‘Scale.’

Intervention development and theory of change:

IPT has its origins in the 1970s through the development of a structured manual to operationalise a supportive psychotherapy in a study of the comparative effectiveness of pharmacological and psychological treatment of depression. It featured in many clinical trials in the following two decades but remained the focus for research study rather than dissemination into practice for much of this period (Ravitz et al, 2017; Weissman and Mootz, 2024).

Two developments signalled a transition towards wider adoption. One was the foundation of the International Society for Interpersonal Psychotherapy (ISIPT) in 2000. This brought together researchers and clinicians from North America, Europe and Australasia to address not only relevant issues of research but also of training and dissemination. This established a major structure that supports global capacity development in IPT to this day. The other key development was the 2001 trial of IPT in post-conflict areas of Uganda, which signalled consideration of IPT as a psychological intervention suited to address mental health issues in low-income and humanitarian settings (WHO and Columbia University, 2016). Of particular

relevance, this involved the use of non-specialist lay providers rather than professional therapists, and a major focus of IPT delivery is now with such personnel. The work of the ISIPT and the deployment of IPT in low-income settings continue as key drivers in the dissemination of the approach.

The initial formulation of IPT was informed by two major bodies of research, the central concepts of which continue to be reflected in IPT whatever its form of delivery. One was attachment literature and, in particular, what happens when individuals experience severance of important attachments. The other was life events research, focused on events that trigger psychopathology. In IPT particular attention is paid to four types of interpersonal crisis: grief, disputes, transitions and loneliness. The central premise of the approach is that helping an individual become aware of these forces shaping their experience and building relevant skills to address them supports recovery. The three phases of treatment – whatever number of sessions are used – seek to respectively identify resources and sources of distress; problem-solve major challenges; and identify learning relevant for the future.

Efficacy and effectiveness:

There is a strong evidence base regarding the efficacy and effectiveness of IPT for the treatment of depression (Ravitz et al, 2017; Weissman and Mootz, 2024). Cuijpers et al. (2011 and 2016) meta-analyses of, respectively, 38 and 60 RCTs involving IPT found overall moderate to large effect sizes for the treatment approach, and non-inferiority to CBT and other psychotherapies. Cuijpers et al. (2021) meta-analysis comparing outcomes of several psychotherapies for depression found IPT to be one of the approaches (along with other interventions including CBT and problem-solving therapy) that demonstrated significant benefits one year after completion of treatment. The most recent meta-analysis of 33 RCTs involving deployment of IPT in the treatment of depression across a broad range of geographies (Weissman and Mootz, 2024) found an overall moderate effect size ($g=0.5$). Importantly, this study found no significant difference in effect sizes by target group (adult, women in the perinatal period or other), by individual or group-based delivery or by whether the interventions were conducted in high-income or low- and middle-income settings. However, average effect sizes were significantly smaller for RCTs with a low Risk of Bias ($g=0.19$ vs. $g=0.58$). Meta-analysis focused on IPT for adolescents (IPT-A) found both group and individual delivery an effective treatment for depression with large effect sizes, and some evidence that improvements were maintained for up to 1 year (Duffy et al., 2019). Large effect sizes documented in reducing depression with adolescents (Zheng et al., 2023) and with older adults (Xu and Koszycki, 2020) has encouraged use with these populations, noting the particular relevance of IPT's emphasis on role transitions with these age groups. None of these studies report major safety issues or harms associated with IPT.

IPT has also been shown to demonstrate moderate effect sizes in addressing anxiety disorders (Markovitz et al. 2014; Weissman and Mootz, 2024). Several trials have also established its effectiveness with respect to PTSD (Althobaiti et al. 2020), with indications of its superiority to exposure-based treatment for those with comorbid major depression.

Stakeholder interviews with clinicians endorsed this perceived utility and effectiveness of IPT in clinical practice: *'it's a model that is easy to apply and it works.'*

Relevance to PLE:

The focus on issues such as grief, role disputes, and life changes identified by beneficiaries in the course of completing the Inventory of Interpersonal Problems is reported to be welcomed by PLE. More generally, the emphasis on interpersonal relationships rather than intrapsychic experience is suggested as an important factor in reducing self-stigma and supporting positive engagement with the approach. The group process of IPT-G is suggested to support the establishment of a supportive community of shared

experience. Increasingly, trials of IPT and IPC-3 have, in the context of documenting processes of contextual adaptation, reported evidence of participatory research and co-creation with targeted communities positively supporting delivery (e.g. Kumar et al, 2022). Congruence with PLE agendas is most clearly illustrated when the use of peer facilitators of IPT-based interventions has demonstrably secured clinical impact (e.g. in veteran-veteran interventions reducing symptoms of PTSD and refugee-refugee work in Peru reducing symptoms of depression and anxiety; Greene et al., 2024).

There is thus substantial evidence of PLE engagement in the development and delivery of IPT, with the focus of local contextualisation of appropriate manuals and the emphasis on training and support of non-professionals and peers clear facilitators of this consistent engagement.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

Resource requirements vary widely with number of sessions, mode of delivery, approach to training and supervision and, more broadly, context. The development of IPC-3 has provided an intervention with significantly less costs for both provider and patient than IPT, although the comparative level of clinical impact has not been reliably established. There is also clear scope for variation in number of sessions for IPT from the standard twelve, which is based upon the initial validation trials of the intervention in the 1970s. In terms of mode of delivery, IPT-G obviously has the benefit of addressing multiple people's needs in one session with, as noted, no major loss in clinical effectiveness. Virtual forms of delivery prompted by the COVID-19 pandemic also potentially reduce resource requirements (Weissman and Mootz, 2024). In terms of training, the competences required to deliver IPT are widely recognised as relatively easy to learn, with one respondent suggesting that after 16 hours of training facilitators can generally deliver IPT reliably (which represents a significantly lower resource investment than is required for CBT, for example). The ISIPT provides a vehicle for therapist certification, which is of value for credentialing mental health workers and developing the workforce in many health systems (although inclusion of IPT training in pre-service education curricula is an appropriate long-term goal). However, the evidence of effectiveness with non-professional facilitators suggests that there are also likely to be significant benefits in strengthening lay capacities for deployment of IPT-based methods. Interviewees reported supervision in support of professional development and quality assurance has proven challenging in several low-resource settings, with a need to integrate support for IPT provision into mainstream service delivery.

In summary, significant attention has been paid over the last decade to identifying – and generally reducing – the resource requirements for delivery and support of the intervention, particularly in low-resource contexts. Several cost-effectiveness studies have indicated IPT to be a resource-efficient intervention (e.g. Johnson et al. 2019, Lal et al. 2021, Rose-Clarke et al. 2022), although such studies reflect major contextual influences on estimates of cost to the health system and individual.

Context, applicability and scalability:

Stakeholder interviews and relevant commentaries articulated a view consistent with the research team's interpretation of the literature during landscape analysis: IPT remains relatively underutilised as an intervention considering its proven efficacy and '*user-friendliness for therapists and patients.*' The universal relevance of the focus on the negotiation of interpersonal losses and transitions during the life course was noted by several sources as a key factor in its wide applicability. A recent publication summarises IPT-based intervention delivery across North America, South America, Europe, Africa, Asia, the Middle East and Oceania (Weissman and Mootz, 2024).

Processes of adaptation have been systematically considered in implementation trials. For example, a recent study of deployment of IPT-G with perinatal adolescents considered adaptations with respect to the Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research, which prompted adjustments of language, number

of sessions and delivery mode (Kumar et al., 2022). Systematic reviews are largely based on studies conducted in high- and middle-income settings, but there is a growing evidence-base indicating effectiveness in low-income settings (Weissman and Mootz, 2024).

In considering strategies for the wider adoption of IPT, two alternative approaches may be observed. One is what one stakeholder referred to as the '*alphabetisation of IPT*,' involving the manualisation of an increasing number of IPT protocols addressing a particular context or condition (e.g. IPT-A and IPT-AST for adolescents, IPT-ED for eating disorders, IIPSRT for bipolar disorder etc.). The other trend is the recognition of the wide transdiagnostic relevance of the core skills and competences deployed in IPT, and the encouragement of their use across mixed caseloads wherever interpersonal factors play into the aetiology, maintenance or management of a condition (i.e. in a manner '*not driven by diagnostic criteria for billing or accountability purposes*'). An example of this latter strategy is consideration within the ISIPT of using IPT to address family systems issues in the onset and management of schizophrenia. There is active debate within the ISIPT community regarding these alternative approaches.

IPT now features in treatment guidelines for depression in the United States, United Kingdom, Canada, and Australia. The WHO version of IPT-G has a significant profile within the group of 'scalable interventions' promoted as part of a stepped-care approach to mental health provision in humanitarian contexts and is now available in eight languages. Despite this progress, stakeholders noted the complex political processes involved in the negotiation of treatment guidelines and the challenge in promoting the use of IPT beyond its '*historically somewhat restricted niche*' in comparison to other interventions (e.g. CBT).

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

IPT represents a valuable route to addressing the treatment gap in provision for depressive and anxiety disorders that represent an increasing proportion of the global burden of disease. With time-limited intervention, impactful delivery through non-professional cadres after modest training inputs and evidence of strong acceptability across a broad range of cultural contexts, IPT (and IPC-3) present a viable approach to addressing mental health needs in low-resource environments (whether this involves socially and economically marginalised communities in high-income settings or wider populations in low- and middle-income countries). Further, the focus on interpersonal relationships and the impacts of loss, transition and isolation renders it coherent and meaningful for individuals faced by humanitarian crisis, including the impacts of climate change (for example, in relation to loss of home or livelihood, inter-group conflict over diminished resources or displacement).

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

IPT has been demonstrated as an effective intervention (generally with moderate to large effect sizes) for depression and an increasing range of other disorders across a wide range of contexts. It is clearly at the stage of 'scale' in terms of our conceptual formulation of the intervention development pipeline. The key factors that have facilitated its progress appear to be the wide cultural relevance of its approach, the sustained investment by intergovernmental and non-governmental organisations in materials and trainings to support its application and the manner in which non-professionals – including peers with lived experience of mental ill-health - have been included in its development and deployment.

However, IPT is not adopted widely as a front-line psychological intervention. The major barriers that have contributed to this appear to be related to the resources and capacities required to deliver the intervention (in terms of trained - specialist or non-professional- workforce, accessibility through the mental health system or equivalent means of provision, means of supervision) and the lack of profile of the intervention in the complex political and professional discussions involved in the negotiation of treatment guidelines.

The recommendations that follow seek to capitalise upon the noted facilitators of advancement while addressing means to circumvent the identified barriers.

In terms of broader lessons learned, the success of scaling IPT is clearly founded on decades of sustained and systematic research committed to exploration of differing formats and contexts of implementation of the core principles of the intervention. The endorsement of the approach through WHO adopting IPT-G as one of the key 'scalable interventions' to support its mhGAP strategy and the sustained work of the ISITP in promoting the intervention also demonstrate factors of potential relevance to the scaling of other interventions.

Recommendations for investment:

As noted above, it is apparent that IPT has advanced in scale and reach significantly over the last decade and that adaptations to delivery, training and supervision enforced by the COVID-19 pandemic have provided a basis for wider application. However, there remain important barriers to widespread adoption, many of which constitute current gaps in the evidence-base that would usefully be addressed to inform efforts at scaling.

Research Recommendations

The following **research related recommendations for investment** suggest systematic means to address these barriers:

- **Identifying influence of 'dose' on clinical effectiveness.** As noted, the typical 'dose' of 12-16 sessions of IPT is linked to the operationalisation and initial validation trials of the intervention in the 1970s. There would be significant value in exploring the range of intervention formats that may be more scalable without major loss of clinical effectiveness e.g. comparative studies of 16, 8, and 4 session IPT and IPC-3 or trials of IPT interventions where the number of sessions is determined by measurable clinical outcomes. There are signs of such studies emerging, but a more concerted effort to document the trade-offs (including in terms of cost-effectiveness) in reduced dose vs. wider access is warranted. Documenting the clinical effectiveness of brief – and thus less resource-intensive – forms of IPT clearly stands to facilitate progress towards wider adoption.
- **Documenting scalable and sustainable models of delivery.** There have, as noted, been significant advances in the provision of training for professionals and non-specialists in IPT methods. However, a major bottleneck in securing wider adoption of IPT is the availability of adequate supervision. There is a knowledge gap with respect to scalable and sustainable models of supervision that can support quality delivery. For example, in synchronous, online supervision are there differences in outcomes with small (~12) vs large (~24) groups of supervisees? One stakeholder noted the potential for the use of artificial intelligence (AI) to review the transcripts of intervention sessions as a quality assurance and supervision measure. Evaluation of the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of such approaches has relevance beyond the case of IPT alone.
- **Evaluation of impact beyond depression.** The evidence-base for IPT in relation to depression is very strong, and indicative of effectiveness with respect to anxiety and PTSD. However, stakeholders indicated that in promoting the use of IPT there was a case to consider its impact with respect to a much broader range of conditions. As noted, there are broadly two alternative strategies in play to address this and advance the progress of IPT to wider adoption:
 - Extend the range of conditions for which a manualised form of IPT is developed and trialled (i.e. furthering the 'alphabetisation' of IPT). One example of such an extension of application

canvassed by one respondent was schizophrenia, addressing the interpersonal issues commonly associated with diagnosis and treatment of the condition. Although not addressing the cardinal symptoms of schizophrenia itself, IPT potentially provides a brief, robust approach to addressing distress associated with the disorder.

- The other strategy is to recognise the potential for IPT to serve as a trans-diagnostic approach. Rather than trials linked to manualised interventions delivered to individuals fulfilling a discrete diagnostic category, studies would examine the impact on a mixed caseload of personalised interventions delivered by an IPT trained therapist.

The former strategy offers the promise of greater standardisation of practice, while the latter potentially provides greater scope for the generalised use of the core principles of IPT.

Ecosystem Recommendations

In addition to the above, it was apparent during the wider consultation that incorporation of any intervention approach into national guidelines was dependent upon political will as well as technical process. Examples were cited of IPT appearing in national guidelines and then being displaced by other approaches because of lobbying from a particular constituency. This suggests two *broader areas of investment*:

- Collate the current evidence-base on efficacy, effectiveness, and cost-effectiveness (and suitable training and supervisory structures) to support relevant advocacy with regulatory bodies regarding inclusion of IPT in treatment guidelines.
- Compile case studies of the inclusion of IPT in treatment guidelines and seek to synthesise principles which have supported relevant evidence-based advocacy. (This work could valuably examine the processes that have also supported the inclusion of other promising, under-utilised interventions in treatment guidelines).

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ISLAMIC TRAUMA HEALING (ITH)

Pipeline stage: Prototype exemplar

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Professor of Psychology and Director of PTSD Research and Treatment Program, Case Western University, Illinois
- Professor of Psychology and Director of Centre for Anxiety and Traumatic Stress, USA Faith-Sensitive MHPSS Lead with major international NGO Clinical Psychiatrist and Founder of Mental Health NGO in Middle Eastern country with majority Muslim population
- Postdoctoral Researcher and former Humanitarian Policy Adviser with major Faith-Based Organisation, UK
- Psychiatrist, Author and Trauma Institute Director Colorado, USA

Target disorders:

PTSD (and comorbidity of depression and anxiety disorders).

Overview:

ITH is a manualised intervention delivered by lay leaders to separate men's and women's groups (typically of 5-7 persons) convened in mosques over six two-hour sessions. It is particularly focused on psychological reactions after trauma exposure (for example in relation to war, natural disasters or sexual assault). It seeks to integrate Islamic and scientific principles of trauma healing in a way that reduces stigma – and strengthens social support – in addressing mental health issues.

Scope:

With implementation focused to date on a single ethnic group (Somali) and with some key data from a recent randomised control trial unpublished, ITH is clearly at the Prototype Exemplar pipeline stage. The review considers the facilitators and barriers influencing the development of ITH and gaps in knowledge that warrant being addressed if progress to the Revise and Test stage is to be made. Additionally, it focuses on the broader lessons that can be drawn regarding the religious framing of psychological interventions that may be of relevance in developing interventions related to other faith traditions.

Intervention development and theory of change:

Islamic Trauma Healing has been developed collaboratively over the last decade by a group of clinical researchers working with Somali Muslims, initially within refugee communities in the USA and latterly in Somaliland (Zoellner et al., 2018; Bentley et al., 2020). There has been input of Islamic leaders and scholars at key stages of defining and refining activities featured in the intervention protocol.

Development was influenced by recognition of the significant unmet mental health needs of Somali Muslim communities, the potential of leveraging Islamic principles and healing practices to support recovery, and the aim of aligning evidence-based psychological strategies with such principles and practices in an integrated intervention (Zoellner et al., 2021). The intervention was from the outset designed as a lay-led, brief intervention delivered in a religious context that provided an accessible and non-stigmatising means to address psychological distress and promote community building and reconciliation.

The intervention seeks to address two key factors sustaining trauma response: avoidance and unhelpful negative beliefs. It does this through activities reflecting Islamic religious practice and belief: a combination of meditative breathing exercises 'Yaa Allah', 'Prophet Narratives' (Qur'anic texts modelling trauma response), imaginal exposure to trauma memories through 'turning to Allah in Dua' and group discussion seeking to promote cognitive restructuring in relation to the narratives considered (e.g. acknowledging trauma and trials in relation to the life of Job/Ayyub; addressing reconciliation with others in relation to the example of the Prophet Muhammad).

Efficacy and effectiveness:

Preliminary trials in the Somali refugee community in Seattle (Zoellner et al. 2018) and in conflict-affected communities of Somaliland (Zoellner et al. 2021) established the feasibility, acceptability and indicative efficacy of the intervention. In the former study, pre-post comparison found large effects (Hedges $g > 1.00$), especially on symptoms of reexperiencing and depression. In the latter study, large, clinically meaningful intervention effects (Hedges g between 1.00 and 2.00) were noted pre- vs post- with respect to PTSD severity, depression and well-being. No major safety concerns are reported in relation to the use of exposure or other aspects of the intervention.

This preliminary work has been followed up with two RCTs, again one in the context of Somali refugee communities in Seattle and the other (a hybrid effectiveness-implementation trial) in nine mosques and three cities in Somaliland. Preliminary analyses of the former indicated a large effect size ($d=0.87$) regarding the primary outcome of PTSD severity compared to waitlist control (Zoellner et al., 2023). Full findings are to be shared on publication. The other RCT is ongoing (Zoellner et al., 2024).

Relevance to PLE:

Preliminary evidence available suggests a high degree of acceptability in targeted populations given the minimisation of stigma through the use of religious narratives and delivery through mosques. Feasibility trials shaping the development of the programme directly examined satisfaction through questions such as '*To what extent did the program[me] match with your religious beliefs and cultural practices?*' and '*Overall, how satisfied are you with the program[me]?*' (Zoellner et al, 2018). The social support secured in the course of the intervention is highlighted in initial evaluations. The ongoing hybrid effectiveness-implementation trial features – in addition to a satisfaction questionnaire - focus groups discussing '*the experience of participating, what was liked most, where ITH needs improvement, barriers to involvement, how to reduce help-seeking stigma, and lessons learned*' (Zoellner et al, 2024).

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

The developers claim that ITH '*has the potential to provide a low-cost, self-sustaining, Islam-based intervention*' (Zoellner et al, 2018). Most fundamentally, the intervention depends upon (a) the relevance of the manualised content to the implementation context and the needs of participants and (b) the capacities of the lay leaders to facilitate the intervention with quality. The content of the intervention has been shaped through an iterative process to address identified mental health concerns and appropriate cultural framing (for instance, opening with the sharing of tea and beginning and closing with the reading a prayer from a local imam). The potential for adaptation of the material for application in other cultural and religious contexts is considered in the next section.

Programme developers seek to establish the required competences in lay leaders for facilitating sessions in four two-hour sessions. Focused on discussion leading skills and group facilitation, this is less intense a training than with many other '*scalable interventions*' but programme developers report high levels of

fidelity to the manualised guide through the course of intervention on the basis of this training. It is the treatment manual that is considered by them to do the *'heavy lifting'* of psychotherapeutic work.

The first study of cost-effectiveness is currently in process. However, ongoing exploration of remote (WhatsApp) supervision (Klein et al., 2023) and an evolving approach to training-of-trainers (to reduce reliance on North American-based expertise) both offer strong potential for identifying cost-efficient routes to implementation.

Context, applicability and scalability:

As noted, the intervention has been developed and trialled in a low-resource conflict setting (Somaliland) and with refugee populations in the USA, indicating its suitability for challenging operating environments. The principle of delivery of the intervention in the setting of the local mosque is key to the approach on the basis that this is a context that is regularly accessed for other purposes (e.g. prayer), is a setting for wider community engagement and a natural place for prayer, reflection and discussion. The context of the mosque also provides the principal basis for the recruitment of lay leaders (although one stakeholder raised concerns at this with regard to the identification and recruitment of female lay leaders, see section on equity considerations).

Interviewees with wide experience of mental health initiatives targeting populations in the Middle East welcomed an approach that sought to be sensitive to the faith traditions of communities and to build upon these rather than ignore them. In the future development of the intervention, they recognised the importance of continued engagement with local leaders (male and female) to discern the nuance of (the variation in) Islamic belief and practice in a given setting to avoid inappropriate or even harmful elements of the implemented programme. The input from Islamic leaders which shaped the current intervention materials for use with Somali communities thus needs to be repeated when revising the material for use with other Muslim communities (i.e. Sunni, Shia, Sufi, Druze, Hanafi, etc.). The extent to which such revisions represent an adaptation of the current intervention or rather more substantive change is potentially key to the scalability of ITH. However, a stakeholder with wide experience of engagement across Muslim communities – having reviewed documentation regarding the intervention - judged that *'the principles drawn upon reflect the basic tenets of Islam and most sects and groups would find them acceptable.'*

Given that 25% of the world's population identifies as Muslim and evidence that Muslims experience the lowest recovery rate from mental health difficulties across all religious groups (Al Harbi, Farrand & Laidlaw, 2023) it would be quite appropriate for pipeline development of ITH to remain fixed upon the goal of establishing a psychological intervention clearly aligned with Islamic principles. Nonetheless, the developers have considered the implications of their work in relation to other religious traditions, and this was a focus of discussion with interviewed stakeholders who had broader experience of promoting mental health and psychosocial support in a *'faith sensitive'* manner (LWF & IRW, 2018). One stakeholder working in the area of inter-religious dialogue with a Christian-based organisation considered that *'the focus on 'stories of faith' in the narrative material used by ITH would potentially be a useful approach within other faith traditions.'* They supported the view of developers that this would most likely best be initially explored with other faiths within the Abrahamic tradition (i.e. Islam, Judaism and Christianity).

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

As noted above, this is an important intervention given evidence regarding the low rates of recovery and barriers to accessing services experienced by many Muslims. Delivery in the context of a local mosque potentially reduces both physical and cultural barriers to service access.

However, some stakeholders raised concerns about the mosque-based delivery of ITH given that in some contexts women are discouraged – or indeed not permitted - to attend mosque. In such contexts explicit measures would need to be taken to engage women in other suitable settings, potentially through the identification of informal female leaders of faith (Rutledge et al., 2020). One stakeholder noted the circumstances in some settings rendered *'the mosque an inadequate space for women,'* suggesting that meetings held in schools, community centres or homes where women met to pray would be more appropriate. Issues of access of Muslim religious minorities to the local mosque also raises questions about equity of access to treatment if the mosque is the only place where the intervention is available.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

Factors that have clearly facilitated the development of ITH over the last decade include:

A committed, multi-institutional research team that have forged strong links to Muslim communities with experience of adversity and developed a coherent pipeline of research studies from exploratory research, through feasibility trials to RCTs; Growing interest and awareness of the role of religious belief and practice in addressing mental health amongst the 80%+ global population that report a religious affiliation; and recognition of Muslim populations as a community for which there are multiple barriers to effective mental health provision.

Apparent barriers to its future scaling include:

Although ITH is clearly in an early stage of development the lack of profile and knowledge regarding the intervention revealed through the consultation and stakeholder interviews is clearly a potential barrier to uptake through potential partnership. Recommendations include actions to address this. As with many other interventions involving non-specialists and volunteers, other potential barriers relate to addressing challenges in establishing effective, efficient and sustainable mechanisms of supervision and, more generally, difficulties in embedding interventions within local systems such that they run beyond a research trial.

In terms of lessons learned, progress in the development of ITH demonstrates the potential for innovation in psychological interventions on the basis of a clearly focused need (access to trauma recovery in Somali Muslim communities) and, as noted above, a committed, multi-institutional team able to mobilise diverse disciplines and networks to bear in specifying a coherent programme of research. However, seeking to operationalise key religious principles and practices in a manner that renders a psychological intervention more accessible and relatable highlights the wide diversity of belief and practice within most faith traditions and, linked to this, a lack of confidence on the part of many organisations to work with interventions explicitly linked to religion.

Recommendations for investment:

There are several current gaps in knowledge of relevance to ITH that warrant addressing if further scaling of the approach is to be achieved:

Research Recommendations

- **Replication of initial RCTs.** With reporting on just a second RCT still due there is clearly a very small – albeit promising – evidence-base supporting development of the intervention. Replication of the intervention with a similar but not identical population (the developers are considering Afghan refugee communities in Seattle) is clearly called for. While this might explore processes of adaptation (see next recommendation) the primary focus would be on consolidation of evidence regarding the existing intervention and further consideration of the influence on moderators such as sex, age and education on outcomes (target inclusion criteria specify a suitable age range of 18-70, but a stakeholder noted the likely impact on participation of wide disparities of age within groups).

- **Generalisability of Muslim religious practices reflected in ITH manual.** To promote advance along the development pipeline research needs to address such questions as: To what extent does the operationalisation of Islamic principles in the current ITH manual reflect practice and belief that is generalisable to non-Somali Muslim communities? What are the processes of adaptation, refinement or substantive revision that may be required for ITH to be acceptable and accessible for wider use within Muslim populations? What are the sensitivities or risks that need to be considered in the process of making the intervention available to these communities?

Ecosystem Recommendations

- **Deeper engagement with the tenets of Islamic Psychology.** ITH represents the integration of some basic Islamic principles and practices with some psychotherapeutic strategies (e.g. management of avoidance, imaginal exposure etc.) established within western psychology. What scope is there for – and what benefits could be gained from a more fundamental engagement with Islamic Psychology? - One stakeholder gave the example of the potential relevance of a theological principle, such as the oneness of God (*Tawhid*) in a therapeutic context as an example of the benefit of more systematic engagement with the extensive literature on Islamic Psychology and mental health (Hartafan et al., 2024).
- **Extension of the ITH programme to other religious communities.** While the three recommendations above address the widening and deepening of engagement with Muslim communities, there is clear potential for adoption of the programme model (in terms of content and means of delivery) with other religious communities. This would involve adjustments to some of the selected '*prophet narratives*' and format of reflective prayers, which (as noted above) would be most feasible within the broad Abrahamic tradition with Jewish or Christian communities. The key research question would be whether the intervention model with these adjustments achieved similar impacts to that reported for ITH.

Other investments of potential relevance would include:

- Profiling ITH – and potentially other related interventions – as an effective and accessible approach to addressing mental health issues in the Muslim communities. One stakeholder – themselves unaware of the development of ITH until alerted to it by this review - suggested that '*there are so many Muslim charities and organisations that are interested in addressing issues of mental health but aren't aware of how to do so.*'
- **Consultation on enhancing access to effective psychological interventions through use of religious framing and practice.** Convening a (global) consultation on the integration of religious practices with proven evidence-based strategies to establish greater access to effective interventions addressing mental disorders. This would draw upon the experience of ITH, but link this to the wider discussions about religious coping strategies and 'faith-sensitive' mental health provision.

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MINDFULNESS-BASED INTERVENTIONS (MBI)

Pipeline stage: Improve and Test

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Psychologist and Associate Professor at a University in Australia
- Research clinical psychologist and book author with various publications about MBCT; Director of a Mindfulness Centre, UK.
- Mental health professional and lived experience expert
- Deputy CEO of a peer mental health network and lived experience expert
- Fieldwork researcher, administrative assistant of a department of military veterans in the African continent and lived experience expert, Kenya
- Lived experience expert, psychologist and implementer, Kenya

Target disorders:

Mindfulness-based interventions (MBI) are used across a wide range of mental health conditions, including **anxiety disorders, depression, bipolar disorder**, eating disorders and stress. MBIs are also used for mental health promotion in the context of diverse chronic physical health conditions such as cancer, cardiovascular disease, and diabetes (Li *et al*, 2024).

Overview of intervention:

The term "mindfulness" refers to two distinct concepts: 1) a meta-cognitive practice that involves intentionally and consistently focusing on the present moment, and 2) reduction of the emotional and cognitive reactivity that arises from the experience, or a state of consciousness marked by a detached awareness of one's thoughts and feelings (Hodann-Caudevilla *et al*, 2020). Whilst there are numerous contemporary applications of mindfulness for wellbeing promotion through in-person group sessions and digital tools, there is a distinct body of mindfulness-based interventions (MBI) that utilise mindfulness in clinical settings to address mental health conditions. These MBI encompass an increasing variety of programs and practices that differ significantly in their underlying theories, content, dosage, and evidence of effectiveness (Klingbeil *et al*, 2017).

Two foundational MBI approaches are Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) and Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT), which are widely used and have strong empirical support. A range of other protocols have been developed based on MBSR and MBCT, each often tailored for specific therapeutic goals. These variations often adjust the programme structure or pedagogical content, but all MBIs share a focus on systematic training on meditation practices to develop mindfulness, which lies at the core of the interventions (Hodann-Caudevilla *et al*, 2020).

Another defining feature of MBIs is their typical in-person group format, often led by one or more instructors who may not necessarily be therapists or mental health professionals, but who possess specific and visible teaching competencies that promote involvement and connection, enabling the effective delivery of MBIs such as interpersonal relational skills, skills in guiding formal mindfulness meditation practices, coverage, pacing, and good organisation of the session curriculum, effective methods for conveying course themes through inquiry, group dialogue, and didactic teaching and competence in managing the group teaching and learning environment (Crane *et al*, 2016). This distinguishes MBIs from other therapies such as acceptance-based approaches like Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) and Dialectical

Behavioural Therapy (DBT) where mindfulness is used as a tool to foster psychological acceptance without the systematic inclusion of meditation practices, but where mindfulness is primarily taught through brief exercises and informal practices centred on daily activities with a focus on the present moment (Hodann-Caudevilla et al, 2020).

Nowadays, with the increasing accessibility and use of modern technologies, digital tools such as app-based MBIs have become important alternatives to in-person delivery. Some advantages of the use of mindfulness apps include lower cost, greater scalability and the ability to maintain anonymity. App users have flexible and on-demand access to therapeutic tools which are customised based on their own data, such as GPS location and symptom levels. Moreover, with the wide availability of smartphones, users can practice their therapeutic skills throughout the day to manage or prevent the exacerbation of symptoms (Linardon et al, 2024).

However, while in-person MBIs often include elements of cognitive therapy, this is not an existing feature for many mindfulness apps tested in research settings. Therefore, there are commercially available mindfulness apps that do not have sufficient evidence from controlled clinical research to support the claims they make about their benefits. This has led to the recent development of various RCTs investigating the clinical utility of mindfulness apps for depression and anxiety (Linardon et al, 2024).

Unlike in-person MBIs, mindfulness apps are usually self-guided, meaning that users do not interact with group members or instructors (Linardon et al, 2024). According to research developed by Matiz et al. (2017), which investigated whether group and single meditation formats led to different outcomes related to mindfulness skills, personality traits, and religious or spiritual self-representations, and to different adherence to training and dropout rates, there is no significant variation between the two meditation formats. The only difference observed was that individual mindfulness had a more profound effect on the character maturity of participants.

Regarding the structure and process of MBIs, both MBCT and MBSR are similar, incorporating 8-weekly sessions of 2-3 hours designed to build mindfulness skills progressively. In-class components include interactive lessons on mindfulness, formal and informal meditative practices, mindful movement and collaborative group discussions to reflect on personal experiences and insights. They can also consist of an all-day retreat dedicated to deepening practice and reflection, and participants are given homework assignments to integrate mindfulness into everyday life routines and activities. MBSR content is typically oriented towards members of the general population dealing with stress, anxiety and chronic pain, and whilst MBCT content significantly overlaps with this, it varies in including other exercises and didactic content specifically relevant to cognition and depression, and targeting individuals with specific vulnerabilities such as depression, anxiety or other mental health conditions (Segal et al, 2002; Li et al, 2024; Santorelli & Kabat-Zinn, 2014).

Scope:

This deep dive focusses on both MBCT and MBSR as they are closely related, with significant overlap between their form and content, and represent the most well-established and evidence-supported MBI approaches.

Intervention development and theory of change:

Mindfulness-based interventions are a diverse set of practices based on concepts derived from Buddhist meditation practices, although most MBIs have removed overt religious elements (Li et al, 2024; Hodann-Caudevilla et al, 2020).

In 1979, Kabat-Zinn pioneered the integration of mindfulness into psychotherapy through the development of a mindfulness-based stress reduction group intervention for the care of individuals living with chronic pain, which was later formalised as Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR). Whilst mindfulness was first developed with the goal of improving the quality of life for individuals dealing with high stress, often related to chronic physical illnesses, over time, its application expanded to other health conditions, particularly due to its positive effects on individuals with psychological issues and somatic diseases. This expansion has been facilitated through various protocols, collectively known as mindfulness-based interventions (MBIs) (Hodann-Caudevilla *et al*, 2020). MBSR has remained a key widely used MBI and was also adapted to create the now well-established Mindfulness-based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT), specifically intended to incorporate elements of cognitive therapy by Segal and colleagues (2002) to reduce risk of relapse in persons recovering from depression. MBCT and MBSR have since been demonstrated to be effective in symptom reduction and recovery from other mental health disorders beyond their original intended target of depression.

There is a lack of consensus on the mechanisms through which MBIs bring about changes in mental health status. Some suggest, for example, that the intentionality, attention, and attitude fostered by mindfulness training leads to a shift in perspective (from subjective to objective) concerning one's internal and external experiences. This influences additional psychological processes that contribute to the desired treatment outcomes. Other potential active change mechanisms posited for mindfulness include increased attention regulation, emotional regulation, behavioural flexibility, reduced rumination, and exposure. Whilst many of these mechanisms relate to similar psychological constructs, there are substantial philosophical and practical differences in how these constructs are defined and applied by different theorists, leading to a lack of consensus about how MBIs produce therapeutic effects (Klingbeil *et al*, 2017). Emerging neuroscience research offers compelling support for these proposed mechanisms. A systematic review by Treves and colleagues (2024) identified a consistent pattern: greater trait mindfulness is associated with decreased reactivity in the amygdala. Given the amygdala's critical role in processing emotions, particularly negative ones, this finding suggests a neural basis for the reduced emotional reactivity often observed following MBI engagement. Furthermore, Treves *et al.*'s (2024) review also highlighted a significant link between higher trait mindfulness and structural changes in key cognitive control regions, specifically increased cortical thickness in the prefrontal cortex (PFC). As the PFC is central to attention regulation and executive functions such as planning and working memory, these structural differences may underlie the enhanced cognitive control capacities often attributed to mindfulness practice, thereby contributing to the therapeutic effects of MBIs. Whilst many of these mechanisms relate to similar psychological constructs, there are substantial philosophical and practical differences in how these constructs are defined and applied by different theorists, leading to a lack of consensus about how MBIs produce therapeutic effects (Klingbeil *et al.*, 2017).

Efficacy and effectiveness:

Overall, the existing evidence suggests that mindfulness-based interventions hold promise in improving clinical symptoms and psychological well-being across various mental health conditions. Evidence suggests that MBCT may be particularly effective for individuals with recurrent conditions. For example, meta-analyses indicate that MBCT significantly reduces the risk of relapse in people with three or more prior episodes of major depressive disorder, with treatment effects being less pronounced in individuals experiencing a first episode (Shapero *et al.*, 2018). This supports the view that MBCT is especially beneficial when individuals have developed ruminative cognitive patterns linked to repeated episodes. Whilst there are several systematic reviews on MBCT, there are few systematic reviews that focus on MBSR, and some reviews fail to distinguish between different MBIs, rendering it challenging to identify the relative effectiveness and efficacy of different models. According to an interviewee, MBCT has successfully

gone through the translational process of developing a practical treatment, and it has become a viable alternative to first-line treatments for many individuals, with research demonstrating that it can be implemented in real-world settings, with its positive effects being sustained over time.

The literature highlights MBIs' effectiveness in depression, schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, and anxiety, as well as their adaptability for culturally specific populations such as First Nations people.

Depression

Meta-analyses of randomized controlled trials provide evidence that MBIs are effective in reducing the relative risk of depressive relapse in individuals with recurrent depression in full or partial remission, decreasing the severity of depressive symptoms in currently depressed individuals post-intervention compared to control groups, and lowering stress levels in non-clinical populations compared to control conditions (Banerjee et al, 2017). A recent meta-analysis, which included four randomised controlled trials involving patients with at least three depressive episodes, demonstrated that MBCT significantly lowered the risk of relapse and recurrence of major depressive disorder when compared to treatment as usual (TAU) or placebo control groups. Furthermore, MBCT has proven to be as effective as maintenance antidepressant medication in preventing the relapse of major depressive disorder. However, studies that have used active control groups structurally similar to MBCT have yielded mixed results concerning its superiority in preventing relapse. These findings suggest that while MBCT may be effective, it may not necessarily be superior to other active psychosocial interventions. It has been suggested that MBCT may be particularly beneficial for individuals with a history of three or more episodes of major depressive disorder, who are especially prone to ruminative thinking. A meta-analysis also found that the number of prior depressive episodes was a significant predictor of treatment outcome for relapse prevention (Shapero et al, 2018).

The findings are mixed regarding the effects of MBCT on depression, with some studies having found no significant improvement in depressive symptoms and others reporting significant reductions (Musa et al, 2020). Notably, Musa et al. (2020) drew on 15 articles with sample sizes ranging from 31 to 219 participants, across countries such as the UK (4 studies), the Netherlands (4), Canada, the USA (2), Italy, Belgium, and Australia. These differences may be linked to specific modifications of the mindfulness interventions across groups (Bojic, Becerra, 2017).

Fisher *et al.* (2023) examined 10 studies (three were conducted in Iran, two in Canada, and one each in Germany, the USA, China, Korea, and India) with a combined sample of 718 participants (sample sizes ranging 38–110) on the effectiveness of MBSR on mental health, HbA1c (a measure of blood glucose), and mindfulness in patients with diabetes, which revealed that MBSR had significant post-intervention effects on anxiety and depression, with large effect sizes (Hedges' $g = -2.407$, $p = .000$ for anxiety and Hedges' $g = -1.110$, $p = .013$ for depression). Additionally, MBSR significantly enhanced mindfulness (Hedges' $g = 1.834$, $p = .021$). However, no significant post-intervention effects were observed for stress (Hedges' $g = -0.409$, $p = .361$) or HbA1c (Hedges' $g = -0.118$, $p = .851$). At follow-up, MBSR continued to show strong benefits for mental health, demonstrating large effect sizes for depression (Hedges' $g = -2.717$, $p = .003$) and stress (Hedges' $g = -1.876$, $p = .037$), along with a sustained improvement in mindfulness (Hedges' $g = 2.683$, $p = .038$). These findings suggest that MBSR is an effective intervention for improving psychological well-being and mindfulness in patients with diabetes (Fisher *et al.*, 2023).

Furthermore, evidence on MBSR demonstrates the effectiveness of the intervention in addressing depression, PTSD, and mindfulness among military veterans. Findings from a review by Li *et al.* (2024) show that within-group comparisons revealed significant reductions in depressive and PTSD symptoms following MBSR, with medium effect sizes. Specifically, MBSR led to a significant decrease in depression (Hedge's $g = -0.501$, $p < 0.001$) and PTSD symptoms (Hedge's $g = -0.475$, $p < 0.001$). Additionally,

mindfulness levels improved among veterans, albeit with a small effect size (Hedge's $g = 0.372$, $p < 0.001$). Notably, treatment effects for depression and mindfulness were maintained at follow-up in between-group comparisons, whereas PTSD symptom improvements were not sustained over time (Li *et al*, 2024). In that review (Li *et al*, 2024), 13 studies were included in total, 11 conducted in the USA and 2 in Iran, covering 1131 participants overall.

Bipolar Disorder

Mindfulness-based Cognitive Therapy, specifically, has shown promising positive effects in managing anxiety symptoms in patients with bipolar disorder and in preventing anxiety from worsening over time. Evidence suggests that MBCT, when combined with pharmacotherapy, may improve cognitive functioning and emotional regulation while also reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression. According to findings from a systematic review by Bojic & Becerra (2017), MBCT appeared to alleviate manic symptoms when participants reported residual mania or hypomania symptoms before the intervention. It is important to note, however, that the review acknowledged several limitations in the existing literature, such as small sample sizes and inconsistencies in the implementation of MBCT across different studies (Bojic, Becerra, 2017).

Psychosis

Evidence considered in Hodann-Caudevilla *et al*'s (2020) systematic review and meta-analysis suggests that MBIs based on the MBCT or MBSR models are effective in treating individuals with schizophrenia spectrum disorders when used alongside treatment as usual, resulting in significant improvements in overall symptomatology ($g = 0.72$). Specific symptom domains also showed notable enhancements, including positive symptoms ($g = 0.32$) and negative symptoms ($g = 0.40$). Additionally, considerable improvements in functional abilities ($g = 1.28$) and illness awareness ($g = 0.65$) have been observed. It has been demonstrated that MBIs are both effective and safe for individuals with schizophrenia, producing outcomes comparable to those of cognitive-behavioural therapy for psychosis. However, it is recommended that these results are interpreted carefully due to the heterogeneity of the interventions and methodological limitations within the studies considered in the analysis. The review evaluated 10 studies with a total of 1094 participants from England, China, Hong Kong, and Taiwan.

Cultural Engagement

A systematic review by Li *et al*. (2024) examined nine studies – carried out in Australia (2), Canada (2), New Zealand (2), and the United States (3) – which involved a combined sample of 125 participants from 11 distinct First Nations groups, including Native American, Canadian First Nations, Metis, Inuit, Māori, Hawaiians, Pacific Islanders, Australian First Nations, Torres Strait Islanders, Confederated Salish Tribe, and the Kootenai Tribe. Evidence from the review demonstrates that MBIs have a positive impact in cultural engagement. The evidence suggests that these interventions successfully adhered to cultural adaptations, fostering high levels of participant satisfaction. Qualitative analyses further reveal that MBIs resonate deeply with the holistic spiritual beliefs of First Nations peoples, providing a meaningful avenue for individuals to reconnect with their cultural and social identities. Moreover, findings show strong participant retention with rates reaching 85.2%, which indicates sustained engagement with the interventions. These findings underscore the adaptability, effectiveness, and feasibility of MBIs for First Nations communities, consistently yielding positive outcomes (Li *et al*, 2024).

While MBIs demonstrate significant benefits, including symptom reduction, improved functioning, and enhanced well-being, further research is needed to refine intervention protocols, address methodological limitations, and explore their long-term effects. Additionally, future studies should examine how MBIs can be tailored to optimise therapeutic outcomes while ensuring cultural sensitivity and sustained engagement.

Relevance to PLE:

An interviewed lived experience expert reflected on their experiences with MBCT and mindfulness-based interventions, both as a trainee therapist and as a client. They reported that mindfulness practices were beneficial and saw MBCT as a value-driven approach that has helped them become more grounded, particularly in navigating the challenges of being neurodivergent and facing systemic issues within various institutions.

Another lived experience interviewee discussed their experience with MBCT from their perspective as a wellness counselling practitioner. They explained that mindfulness, when integrated into therapy, is holistic approach that considers the emotional, cognitive, physical, and even spiritual dimensions of well-being, but that not everyone is ready to engage with it in a therapeutic context. They pointed out that some people struggle with the idea of mindfulness practice, especially when they fear it might conflict with their personal religious beliefs [because of its origins in Buddhist practice]: *“For me, it was more about how do you get people to understand what it means, because people immediately believe that mindfulness is going to take their religion away and they do not want that, so there is this misperception, and maybe just not enough information and literacy on what it means”*. The interviewee emphasised the need for more education and understanding around mindfulness. This interviewee also shared how MBCT was greatly beneficial to them personally during hospitalisation for their mental health condition. Indeed, it was this experience that inspired them to subsequently integrate mindfulness into the wellness counselling practice they began after recovery.

Another PLE interviewee discussed how mindfulness has helped them recognise how their mental health symptoms manifest, and this recognition of when their depression may be *“resurfacing”* supported coping that prevented their challenges from escalating. They emphasised the importance of MBCT in helping them recognise when they need to seek support, talk to someone, or make changes in their behaviour to better cope with their emotions: *“I was going through a lot of problems, encountering PTSD and major depressive disorder. So, mindfulness helps with being aware of your emotions at a specific time and focus on the here and now. You put aside everything that is not relevant at that time. So, it is a more focused type of an intervention on yourself and your emotions at the moment.”*

A interviewee with lived experience shared how mindfulness, initially encountered through a workplace wellness workshop, was extremely helpful for them during a period when they were struggling with PTSD and major depressive disorder. They found daily mindfulness practices to be extremely beneficial for dealing with their mental health challenges and reported that it was now a part of their everyday life as a key resource, not only to manage their mental health condition but also to deal with other aspects of their lives, such as work and family, *“It is a long-term solution, actually, for me. It is an empowerment. Since you will be able to use it in your daily living it’s not just about dealing with your psychological problems, but also with your problem solving and challenges at work or in your family or in any other challenge that you go through.”* Although initially introduced through a structured group setting, they continued the practice independently.

Several lived experience interviewees affirmed mindfulness-based techniques as being empowering and giving people with mental health conditions the capacity to deal with challenging emotional and mental states, reducing dependence on external support. Regarding accessibility, a South African lived experience interviewee highlighted that mindfulness was not commonly practiced by many mental health professionals in their area, which limits its widespread use. They noted that few practitioners had formal training in mindfulness-based approaches, and that these practices were rarely integrated into public or community mental health services, making access dependent on private or informal channels. There

wasn't explicit discussion of whether app-based support for mindfulness-based interventions were a viable alternative to overcome these access barriers.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT) has been shown to be a cost-effective alternative to conventional treatments for individuals with depression. According to Zhang et al. (2022), MBCT also benefits adults with a history of major depressive episodes who are in remission, helping prevent relapse. A specific adaptation—MBCT with support to taper or stop antidepressant medication (MBCT-TS)—was found to save approximately \$439 (equivalent to \$673 in 2020) per relapse averted and \$23 (equivalent to \$35 in 2020) per disease-free day gained, compared to continued maintenance antidepressant medication (m-ADM). However, further studies among patients with multiple depressive episodes found that MBCT-TS was not more effective or more cost-effective than m-ADM on its own. Both approaches showed enduring effectiveness, and it has been suggested that combining them may offer complementary benefits.

Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) has also demonstrated cost benefits, particularly in reducing overall healthcare expenditures across a variety of physical and mental health conditions. Its use has been associated with alleviating financial burdens on healthcare systems by lowering reliance on more intensive services. Evidence suggests that MBSR provides a cost-effective treatment option, particularly for high-risk patient groups.

Other mindfulness-based interventions may also offer cost-saving potential, especially when adapted for specific populations or delivered through scalable formats. However, these approaches are less frequently evaluated in economic terms. Further research is needed to assess their relative effectiveness and cost-efficiency across diverse contexts.

Context, applicability and scalability:

Mindfulness-Based Interventions (MBI) have been successfully implemented in diverse contexts, including within clinical or primary health settings. Despite the Buddhist origins of mindfulness practice, the secular nature of most MBIs has meant that these have been implemented within a variety of social, cultural and institutional contexts.

The review by Li *et al.* (2024) highlights the adaptability, effectiveness, and feasibility of MBIs for First Nations peoples, consistently yielding positive outcomes. However, it was identified that meaningful cultural adaptations are necessary to move beyond "*white mindfulness*," with a "*semi-universal*" model that blended standard MBSR practices with culturally grounded themes, indigenous values, traditions, and perspectives being observed to enhance MBIs' relevance and reception. Li et al. (2024) reported challenges of implementing MBIs with indigenous communities included the lack of childcare for participants, uncertainty about other (cross-cultural) instructors' teaching competency, miscommunication and disagreements among the instructors, the complexity and type of language used, cultural proficiency of the non-indigenous instructor, and quality of room and infrastructure.

A key aspect of cultural adaptation is applying the ecological validity and cultural sensitivity model, ensuring interventions are both effective and culturally appropriate. Collaboration between mindfulness practitioners and persons with contextual and cultural knowledge and community members is crucial to ensuring MBIs are aligned appropriately with local practices and framings. Tailoring MBIs to different cultural contexts enhances relevance, engagement, and outcomes. Programs that incorporate local traditions, languages, and community practices show higher adherence and effectiveness. In parallel, investment in innovative delivery methods - such as virtual reality and AI-driven mindfulness coaching -

can improve accessibility and personalisation, making mindfulness training more adaptable to diverse needs.

A lived experience expert stressed the importance of adapting mindfulness to fit different cultural contexts and highlighted the accessibility challenges in places like South Africa, where many people live in villages without easy access to healthcare settings where MCBT was typically provided. Digital formats, including online courses and mobile apps, have demonstrated positive outcomes and can bridge accessibility gaps, particularly in underserved areas. Funding should prioritise the development and evaluation of these scalable solutions, ensuring they maintain engagement and effectiveness. On the other hand, while it is relatively easy to make these interventions accessible internationally at scale with modern digital tools, there remain significant challenges to determine what works for whom, how to target interventions effectively, and how to integrate them into a structured care pathway. The biggest hurdle, according to an interviewee, is ensuring that interventions are reaching the right people in the most effective way.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion

Li *et al.* (2024) found that MBIs often reflect Western, individualistic frameworks that overlook systemic inequities affecting First Nations peoples. "*White mindfulness*" can disregard the impacts of racism and colonisation, making these interventions less accessible and relevant. To promote inclusivity, they suggest that MBIs should address intergenerational trauma, power imbalances, and social conditioning while integrating different languages, traditions, and values. For example, the review identified studies that were co-created with the active involvement of First Nations peoples resulting in adaptations in terminology to reflect indigenous culture and holistic health perspectives. Some studies utilized metaphors relevant to First Nations populations, including traditional prayers and characters inspired by Māori stories, while others integrated elements such as traditional meeting places from their respective First Nations cultures, such as sharing circles and sweat lodges, traditional ceremonial practices, such as the karakia prayer, and traditional mindsets, such as the aloha and mahalo concepts. Moreover, a few of the analysed studies adapted the goals of MBIs to the specific needs of social groups, such as alleviating race-based stress for black individuals.

Additionally, socioeconomic barriers, including financial costs and time constraints, can limit participation in MBIs, particularly for individuals with low incomes or in areas with poor health coverage. Ensuring accessibility for people with disabilities is also critical for equitable engagement. This includes providing accommodations for mobility, sensory, and cognitive needs.

Facilitators may need to actively address stigma to create safe and supportive spaces, especially for individuals from historically marginalised communities.

As previously noted, MBIs must acknowledge diverse cultural perspectives on mindfulness, mental health, and healing. By addressing these equity concerns, MBIs can become more inclusive, relevant, and effective for diverse populations.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

The findings of a systematic review by Hodann-Cudevilla *et al* (2020) indicate that mindfulness-based interventions are effective in treating individuals with schizophrenia spectrum disorders when used alongside treatment as usual. However, existing empirical evidence on the effectiveness of MBIs on schizophrenia was found to be limited. Therefore, authors indicate that further studies are needed in this population that adhere to high methodological standards and include sample sizes large enough to ensure the validity of the results (Hodann-Caudevilla *et al*, 2020).

Some common study limitations were found across the literature on MBCT interventions for people with bipolar disorder, including small sample sizes, lack of control groups, variations in the MBCT interventions, noncompliance with or non-reporting of homework assignments, and insufficient monitoring and reporting of adverse effects and factors contributing to attrition rates (Bojic, Becerra, 2017).

According to an interviewee, MBIs can also be preventive approaches with compelling cost-effectiveness and strong arguments in their favour, but when faced with a choice between treating mental health problems or focusing on prevention, healthcare systems tend to prioritise, and sometimes even exclusively focus on, treatment. Other barriers include the availability of sufficiently trained therapists, support from top-level leadership, and adequate resources. Many leaders in mental health and healthcare systems are more accustomed to models that prioritise measurable, biomedical approaches to treatment. In contrast, MBIs are rooted in 'mind-body medicine', which integrates physiological, psychological, and behavioural dimensions of care. This orientation can sometimes face resistance, as it diverges from conventional frameworks that emphasise pharmacological interventions or narrowly defined clinical protocols. While this challenge is not unique to MBIs, their emphasis on self-regulation, awareness, and experiential learning may make them less immediately aligned with dominant service models. Expanding understanding of mind-body approaches and their evidence base may help shift perceptions and increase institutional acceptance.

Recommendations for investment:

Research Recommendations

- **Improve quality of evidence through supporting randomised control trials with larger sample sizes and rigorous methodologies.** Investment in mindfulness-based interventions (MBIs) should prioritise strengthening the evidence base through high-quality randomised controlled trials with larger and more diverse samples. As highlighted in the "Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and research in this space" section, limitations in current evidence include small sample sizes and methodological inconsistencies. Studies should assess the impact of MBCT and MBSR not only as standalone interventions but also in combination with treatment-as-usual (TAU), and compare these against TAU alone. Given the variability in findings, research should clarify which populations benefit most from MBIs, the optimal duration and intensity of interventions, and their long-term effectiveness across different mental health conditions. It is also important to address potential self-selection bias, as individuals who enroll in mindfulness studies may be more open to experiential or introspective practices than those who would opt for medication-based approaches. Additionally, rigorous cost-effectiveness analyses can determine their value relative to other psychological therapies.

Ecosystem Recommendations

- **Incorporating MBIs into a population health framework.** An interviewee stated that there's a growing shift towards incorporating Mindfulness-Based Interventions (MBIs) into a population health framework by focusing on holistic approaches that involve cardiologists, dietitians, nutritionists, public health experts, and even regular gym instructors. If mental health can be improved at a population level, fewer people will need acute services. An important part of this shift is how we communicate these ideas. It's not necessarily through academic journals. In mental health, there could be a target for individuals who are already well but want to become even healthier. The broader global health perspective moves beyond just being well to also addressing states of thriving. Tailoring messages to specific audiences about what works for whom, and how, could make a difference. The same applies to the policy space. Many people designing healthcare systems and trying to create cost-effective systems don't always have access to all the information they need, but researchers already know a lot about what works and they are not always reaching the people responsible for implementing those

solutions. This aligns with the "Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness" section, which suggests MBIs can be cost-saving and reduce healthcare expenditures.

- **Optimising the scope of MBCT.** According to an interviewee, historically, Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT) has been effective in helping people step back from negative thought and emotional patterns, allowing them to respond in healthier ways. However, research suggests that if individuals are also encouraged to engage with positive experiences and cultivate the ability to appreciate things, it can lead to even greater outcomes. When people start to experience mastery or take pleasure in being connected with others, the benefits are more significant. It is promising to continue expanding the scope of MBCT to include these positive aspects, which could lead to even greater gains in mental health and well-being. This builds upon the discussion of MBCT's efficacy and effectiveness for conditions like depression and bipolar disorder, as detailed in the "Efficacy and effectiveness" section.

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PROBLEM MANAGEMENT PLUS (PM+)

Pipeline stage: Improve and Test

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Scalable Mental Health Intervention Lead for Major International Organisation Clinical Psychology
- Researcher and Educator, United Kingdom Community Worker Leading PM+ implementation in city
- Clinical Social Worker with Experience and Mental Health Lead for Donor Organisation, USA

Target disorders:

PM+ addresses adults' experience of common mental disorders, principally depression and anxiety. However, given its wide use in situations of adversity, it has also been used in populations vulnerable to post-traumatic stress disorder.

Overview of intervention:

Problem Management Plus (PM+) is a manualised intervention generally delivered over five sessions in individual or, increasingly, group format (typically with between 8 and 12 participants). It was one of the first 'low intensity' (now termed 'scalable') interventions developed by WHO seeking to respond to the mhGAP strategy to strengthen capacity of non-specialists to address mental health disorders. It integrates problem-solving and behavioural treatment techniques of established efficacy in a structure shown to be suited to delivery in a variety of formats. PM+ has been adapted into multiple delivery formats to enhance scalability and reach, including the group-based version (Group PM+) and a digital self-help intervention (Step-by-Step). Each session addresses a distinct strategy (e.g. stress management, behavioural activation etc.) and lasts for between two and three hours (although Step-by-Step is clearly self-paced).

Scope:

This review focuses on the barriers to - and facilitators of - the progress of PM+ along the development pipeline since its establishment in 2015. The intervention is currently classified at the Improve and Test stage because its implementation and evaluation have largely been confined to LMIC settings and humanitarian populations, although growing evidence of its use in a wider range of geographies suggests it is close to categorisation as at the stage of Scale. The review seeks to identify evidence gaps that would support this transition towards wider adoption.

Intervention development and theory of change:

The Ideation phase for PM+ was rooted in the needs identified during the development of mhGAP. A group of twenty-four international experts convened to develop a prototype of a five-session intervention package integrating problem-solving and behavioural treatment techniques of established efficacy. Funds were then secured for two fully powered RCTs of PM+ in Kenya and Pakistan, both of which involved extensive cultural adaptation to ensure relevance in these settings.

Building on these studies, Terre des hommes secured funding to document processes of implementation and adaptation of PM+ in three humanitarian contexts, with the specific remit of identifying barriers and facilitators to scaling. With studies demonstrating the feasibility of group-based delivery (e.g. Acaturk et al., 2022), an RCT in Nepal established the clinical effectiveness of Group PM+ with respect to psychological distress and depression (Jordans et al., 2021).

Efficacy and effectiveness:

The initial RCTs in Pakistan and Kenya showed PM+ to have medium to large effect sizes on symptoms of anxiety and depression and somewhat smaller, although still significant, effects on symptoms of PTSD (Rahman et al., 2016; Bryant et al., 2017). Several studies have subsequently reported moderate to large effect sizes regarding symptoms of PTSD (e.g. de Graff et al., 2020). De Graff et al. (2024) found clinical impact of PM+ on anxiety (and depression in men) to be retained at one-year follow-up with Syrian refugees in the Netherlands. An RCT in Nepal (Jordans et al., 2021) established the efficacy of Group PM+, albeit with small to medium effect sizes in relation to symptoms of depression and PTSD. However, this study valuably established the utilization of the behavioural strategies targeted in PM+ sessions to predict outcomes, suggesting that follow-up booster sessions may be a valuable means of increasing clinical impact.

Mwangala et al. (2024) recently collated findings from 14 RCTs and 2 pre-post trials of PM+ which consistently reported moderate-to-large effect sizes in relation to anxiety and depression, although there was wide variation in the quality of studies included. Schafer et al. (2023) completed a systematic review and meta-analysis of 23 studies including 5,298 participants. Overall, they found small to moderate (0.31-0.45) effect sizes of the intervention but again noted major heterogeneity across studies and concluded that the certainty of evidence was very low across all outcomes. Importantly, they found no evidence of differential outcomes for PM+ delivered to individuals, Group PM+ and the digital intervention, Step-by-Step.

In summary, the evidence base for PM+ is robust, with multiple RCTs and systematic reviews consistently demonstrating moderate-to-large effect sizes in reducing anxiety, depression, and PTSD symptoms. Findings from diverse settings, including humanitarian contexts, support the intervention's adaptability and scalability. However, significant heterogeneity across studies, concerns about study quality, and limited long-term follow-up data highlight research gaps.

Through the EU-funded STRENGTHS consortium and other initiatives, several feasibility and pilot studies (e.g. de Graff et al., 2020; Spaaij et al., 2023) explored alternative delivery formats for PM+ including peer-to-peer, telephone-based and digital interventions. The intervention has also adapted to address specific conditions with the incorporation of additional modules, leading to the development of PM+A to address alcohol misuse (Fuhr et al., 2021) and PM+EP, which incorporates emotional processing to address symptoms of PTSD (Sever et al., 2021).

By early 2024 the extent of scaling was indicated by a scoping study identifying published reports on PM+ implementation in at least 19 countries, largely LMICs or amongst refugee populations in high-income settings (Mwangala et al., 2024). In addition, significant steps towards adoption have been made with the specification of PM+ in the IASC MHPSS Minimum Service Package in humanitarian emergencies and the recent WHO guidance on integrating PM+ and other evidence-based psychological interventions into existing services.

The theory of change for the intervention, regardless of its delivery format, is based upon the provision of four core strategies: stress management, problem solving, behavioural activation and strengthening social support. These strategies are typically introduced following a psychoeducation component focused on common reactions to adversity (Mwangala et al., 2024).

Only in the case of the digital version of the intervention Step-by-Step does this differ, with the omission of the problem-solving elements enforced by technical restrictions of the modality.

Relevance to PLE:

Reports regularly document the high acceptability and positive feedback from participants in PM+ and reports of adverse events are rare. Stakeholders interviewed reinforced how the introduction of PM+ can serve as an effective means of addressing issues of mental health in communities where there is significant stigma associated with the subject.

PLE engagement is generally a key feature of the processes of contextualisation that form a core foundation for PM+ implementation (Coleman et al., 2021). Dowrick et al. (2022) detail the extensive stakeholder engagement with refugees with lived experience of mental ill health in the process of establishing the feasibility and adaptation of PM+ for use with this population in the north-west of England. Their report documents the focus and approach of PM+ being seen as highly relevant and non-stigmatising.

Stakeholders interviewed for this review described similar processes of PLE engagement in preparation for implementation of PM+ with other populations, with similar positive reports of the approach fostering acceptability and engagement: *'it has empowered communities to address issues that were formally taboo'*. The use of peers – including persons who have shared exposure to stress and trauma - as facilitators of PM+ interventions documented in several studies (e.g. de Graff et al., 2020; Spaaij et al., 2023) further reinforces evidence that PM+ provides a basis for strong engagement with persons with lived experience of mental ill health across a diverse range of contexts.

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

Core resources to deliver PM+ comprise the manual and associated materials, trained facilitators for the five sessions of the intervention, and the training, support and supervisory structures to sustain delivery. The detailed, WHO-endorsed, freely accessible manual (now available in over twenty languages) is widely considered a major facilitator promoting the uptake of PM+. Although there are examples of mental health professionals (e.g. psychologists) acting as facilitators, the vast bulk of reports document deployment of non-professionals in the role (generally community members with a minimum of completed secondary education). Training, support and supervision thus represent the major focus of professional support – and major resource demand - for implementation of PM+.

There are consistent claims made regarding the cost-effectiveness of PM+ based upon the relatively low-resource requirements of provision by non-specialist providers and the consistent positive impacts on clinical outcomes. Nonetheless, formal cost-effectiveness analyses have been infrequent. De Graff et al. (2020) found PM+ significantly more costly than care-as-usual for intervention with Syrian refugees in the Netherlands, though projected productivity losses averted rendering the intervention cost-effective. In relation to an intervention in Pakistan, Hamdani et al., 2020 found PM+ between 5 and 20 times more costly than enhanced usual care, which suggests challenges in securing wider scaling. A significant proportion of those additional costs were related to supervision (the higher estimate being based on international support for this function) which signals a major bottleneck in seeking to establish PM+ within low-resource mental health systems. Nonetheless, given the clinical impact of the intervention even modest estimates of levels of 'willingness to pay' in that context indicated a 90% probability of the intervention being a cost-effective use of resources compared with enhanced usual care.

Context, applicability and scalability:

PM+ was designed from the outset to address mental health issues for people facing situations of adversity. Early implementation was focused on populations in the context of humanitarian emergencies, often compounded by other risks (e.g. exposure to gender-based violence). The bulk of current use remains focused in LMIC and/or humanitarian contexts, where non-governmental organisations are the principal providers, and the work is dependent upon humanitarian or other forms of non-recurrent funding.

The wide use of PM+ in the humanitarian and development sectors has demonstrated that the intervention has applicability across a wide range of cultural contexts. While this provides evidence of potential scalability, the challenges of sustainability of provision in low-resource settings with dependence on short-term funding are extreme and recurrent. Issues of sustaining quality of provision through retention of facilitators and maintenance of supervision are highlighted in many of the case studies featured in a special issue of the journal, *Intervention*, focused on the scaling of PM+ (Ager et al., 2021).

One response to the resource demands to sustain provision of PM+ in such settings – and to seek clear connection with other available mental health resources – is explicit implementation of PM+ within a ‘stepped care’ approach. This sees other, less resource-intensive interventions deployed in initial response to psychological distress with enrolment offered for interventions such as PM+ for those for whom more intensive support is required (Keyan et al., 2024). This approach commonly sees other WHO resources such as the psychoeducational ‘Doing What Matters in Times of Stress’ and the self-paced Self-Help Plus deployed before individuals are considered for PM+. Stepped care further provides a basis of identifying people who may warrant referral to specialised mental health services – if they are feasibly available – on the completion of the PM+ intervention. This stepped care principle was reported by stakeholders to operate in the context of mental health provision for asylum-seekers and refugee populations in high income settings, with PM+ providing a basis for referral to appropriate additional forms of mental health support.

While there remain significant challenges to the sustained scaling of PM+ in low-resource settings, the wider potential for scaling is evidenced by examples of ‘reverse innovation’ in the form of use of PM+ as an innovative solution to address emerging mental health needs in high income settings. While many examples of PM+ use in such contexts remain focused upon asylum-seeking and refugee populations (e.g. Sever et al., 2021; Dowrick et al., 2022) there are some recent indications of use with other populations e.g. initiatives in response to the Covid-19 pandemic with healthcare workers in Europe (RESPOND, 2025) and online support to marginalised populations in New York accessed through community organisations (Pfeffer et al., 2023).

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

The design and deployment of PM+ as an intervention suited to low-resource settings with poor coverage of mental health conditions indicates its clear relevance to addressing global equity in mental health provision. The literature documents extensive evidence of applicability at scale in low- and middle-income countries (and, as noted above, with marginalised groups in high-income settings). Developments such as PM+A point the way towards adoption in the context of substance use in a manner of wide relevance to youth populations and others (Fuhr et al., 2021).

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

Several recent studies have explicitly considered factors that may serve as barriers to or suitably addressed, facilitators of PM+ scaling (e.g. Woodard et al., 2022; Woodward et al., 2023; Spaaij et al., 2023). The majority of these have noted the central importance of resources to ensure continuity of appropriate supervisory support and quality control. These resources include sustainable sources of funding and linkage with the existing health system (or some other structure for accreditation and supervision of non-specialist PM+ helpers). Currently lack of these resources is, however, regularly cited as a barrier to scaling

In terms of specific facilitators of implementation of PM+ the accessibility of materials is widely noted and was highlighted by interviewed stakeholders. This accessibility relates to the open access to the core manuals and related training materials but also to the very structured approach and focus on concrete

skills and strategies of PM+ which fosters understanding amongst both participants and facilitators. Its adaptability to differing cultural contexts and feasibility of delivery through multiple formats have clearly been further facilitators of moves towards scale.

Offering an intervention that has demonstrable clinical benefits in five sessions has also been a facilitator, although the potential for costs to be lower (and thus scaling to be easier) with less sessions was noted in earlier consultations and reinforced during stakeholder interviews. In these terms, the resource demands of the usual five session structure are in some contexts a barrier to wider use, which is flagged later as an issue warranting exploration. Problem solving strategies are already omitted from the digital version of PM+, Step-by-Step without apparent loss of clinical impact. Consultations indicated scope for 'remixing' elements of PM+, exploring reduction in the number of delivered sessions or – noting the potential value of reinforcing use of strategies – adding 'booster' sessions sometime after receiving the standard (or reduced) number of sessions.

The most consistent barrier to wider scaling of PM+ cited in the literature and in stakeholder interviews related to sustainable structures of supervision. As noted in a previous section, and above, this is closely linked to the short-term funding on which initiatives to roll-out PM+ are commonly dependent. 'Mainstreaming' PM+ within (strengthened) national mental health provision is being addressed in several contexts. For example, Coleman et al. (2021) describe efforts to '*adapt PM+ for routine delivery across multiple public sector primary care and community settings in partnership with Ministries of Health*' in Rwanda, Peru, Mexico and Malawi. Stakeholders interviewed also noted the potential value of training in PM+ featuring within the pre-service training curricula of psychologists and social workers in high-income settings. This would equip a much larger cadre of health professionals to support delivery of PM+ and related scalable interventions. Health professional specialists may not be crucial to scaling PM+ while maintaining quality, however. Greene et al. (2024) compared outcomes and costs for Group PM+ delivered by non-specialists who received training and supervision from a psychologist or a trained non-specialist. There were no differences in clinical outcomes between these two supervision models. However, while attendance was higher in groups whose facilitator was trained and supervised by the psychologist, groups run by non-specialists supervised by other trained non-specialists demonstrated higher fidelity to Group PM+ guidance and lower implementation costs.

Lessons learned from the experience of PM+ over the last decade highlight factors that facilitate the development of the intervention and help overcome identified barriers. The convening of a wide technical group to specify core skills and strategies to address in a brief manualised intervention secured broad ownership of the intervention, which was further bolstered by WHO-endorsement and prompt establishment of clinical efficacy through robust trials in real-world settings. Momentum was established through engagement with a broad range of non-governmental agencies in implementing, refining and evaluating the intervention. Further development of the intervention has been marked by innovation in terms of delivery mechanisms, successful advocacy for incorporation in global treatment guidelines and openness to 'reverse innovation' informing service development in high-income settings. Many of these advances have clearly been supported by engagement with potential users of services, ensuring cultural and lived experience perspectives shape implementation.

Recommendations for investment:

Research-related recommendations:

While there has been a rapid accumulation of evidence regarding PM+ over the last decade, the above analysis has indicated significant gaps in knowledge relevant to strategies to address continuing barriers to - or capitalise more effectively on identified facilitators of - pipeline progress.

- **Pursuing deeper analysis of existing studies.** While there is a case for commissioning further research, much may be learned from deeper analysis of the many existing studies conducted over the last decade. The meta-analysis of Schäfer et al. (2023) is an illustration of the sort of insight that can be drawn from analysis of just 23 existing studies regarding effectiveness and the influence of moderators (such as format of intervention or age of participants). With a continued accumulation of research evidence, emerging approaches such as IPDMA (individual participant meta-analysis) offer the prospect of identifying predictors of key variables (such as dropout, suicidal ideation etc.) and modelling impacts of variations in delivery (e.g. mode of delivery, number of sessions attended, prior exposure to other stepped-care interventions such as SH+) through systematic analysis of pre-existing datasets.
- **Research on key moderators of clinical effectiveness.** As noted, systematic reviews have identified effect sizes ranging from large to moderate to small across existing studies. The varied quality of published studies and the high risk of bias in many makes it difficult to judge the typical clinical impact that may be secured through PM+ and, crucially, the factors that will strengthen outcomes. While IPDMA analysis of existing studies is warranted, a small number of robust, well-powered trials would substantially strengthen the evidence-base as a foundation for wider adoption. These may usefully be conducted in middle- or high-income settings to support advocacy for adoption in such settings.
- **Implementation research on models of facilitator supervision and stepped care.** These are the two areas of study most crucial to the mechanisms of scaling up PM+ implementation. Building on the work of Greene et al. (2024), implementation research needs to identify models for supervision of non-specialist facilitators that are viable and sustainable given the prevailing capacity of health and social welfare institutions, availability of mental health specialists and recurrent expenditure available for mental health provision in each implementation context. Also, the most effective and efficient place of PM+ within a stepped care model of mental health provision needs to be determined through implementation research documenting different configurations of provision and the clinical outcomes, retention, rates of referral and costs associated with each.
- **Extension of analyses of cost-effectiveness.** The evidence-base on cost-effectiveness of PM+ is clearly sparse, but points to the potential of such evidence to inform service planning in terms of the inclusion of PM+ and similar focused interventions deliverable by non-specialists. Rigorous cost-effectiveness data across a range of low-, middle- and high-income countries stands to provide a strong foundation for advocacy for the wider adoption of PM+ in these settings.

Ecosystem Recommendations

It is striking that the benefits of a brief psychological intervention of established clinical effectiveness in addressing anxiety, depression and PTSD - and which is of moderate cost and well accepted by persons with lived experience of mental ill-health – have largely been experienced only by persons in LMICs and marginalised groups within high-income settings. While the targeting of PM+ to persons in situations of such adversity is to be welcomed, the potential role of the intervention in addressing the mental health treatment gap more widely has been largely neglected. This suggests two important areas of investment:

- Promoting, documenting and profiling the roll-out of PM+ with a broad mental health outpatient population in several high- or middle-income settings. Building on recent developments such as the initiatives with health workers in Europe and communities in New York noted above, support demonstration of the proof of concept of PM+ as an appropriate, generalised intervention strategy addressing anxiety, depression and PTSD.

- **Support advocacy for promoting adoption of PM+ within comprehensive mental health provision.** Use data, personal testimonies and policy insights gained from 1. above – along with the wider evidence-base regarding PM+ - to develop an explicit advocacy strategy to include PM+ within national and international treatment guidelines and thus complete its progress to the pipeline stage of widespread adoption.

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PROBLEM SOLVING THERAPY (PST)

Pipeline stage: Scale (Partial)

Stakeholders interviewed:

- Research Clinical Psychologist, USA, Professor of Global Mental Health, United Kingdom

Target disorders:

It is commonly used to address depression, but it has also been applied for anxiety, PTSD and other mental health disorders. It has a potential for a transdiagnostic role where its effectiveness comes from targeting core cognitive and behavioural processes that underlie various psychological disorders.

Overview of intervention:

PST is a structured, cognitive-behavioural approach designed to enhance an individual's ability to cope with challenges and stressors by improving problem-solving skills. Widely used in mental health, primary care, and community settings, PST serves as a transdiagnostic intervention for various psychological and emotional difficulties. It is typically a short-term intervention, delivered in between 4 to 12 sessions depending on the setting and individual needs. PST targets two key areas: problem orientation, which helps individuals shift from a negative mindset (e.g. avoidance, hopelessness) to a positive one (e.g. confidence, active coping) and problem-solving skills, which focus on teaching systematic steps to effectively approach and resolve problems. PST focuses on four core skills to promote adaptive problem solving: (1) defining the problem; (2) brainstorming possible solutions; (3) appraising solutions and selecting the best one; and (4) implementing the chosen solution and assessing the outcome (Metz et al, 2023).

Scope:

The focus of this review is identifying barriers and opportunities to wider scale-up of use of PST as a psychological intervention and research gaps in current knowledge that, if addressed, may support advancement to wider adoption.

Intervention development and theory of change:

The development of PST is rooted in social problem-solving theory and cognitive-behavioural principles, designed to help individuals systematically address and resolve life challenges. Initially developed by D'Zurilla and Nezu (1982), PST was based on the idea that ineffective problem-solving contributes to psychological distress. The theory and practice of PST have been refined and revised over the years by D'Zurilla, Nezu and their associates (Nezu et al., 2012). PST was initially developed to address depression and stress-related disorders. Over time, it has been adapted for use in treating a wide range of health and mental health problems, including anxiety, chronic illness management, and various other emotional and psychological difficulties. Its development involved empirical testing, demonstrating effectiveness across various populations, leading to refinements such as brief therapy formats and digital interventions. PST teaches individuals a systematic and stepwise approach to identify and solve problems based on the rationale that developing the skills to address life stressors decreases the negative impact of these stressors on mood and wellbeing by helping individuals cope more effectively with stressful problems (Metz et al., 2023). Emotion-Centred PST (EC-PST) is a recent development of the approach – currently

under evaluation (Beaudreau et al., 2023) – which seeks to incorporate more recent advances in neuropsychology and the impact of emotions on problem-solving.

There is a clear theory of change suggesting how structured problem-solving leads to improved mental health outcomes (Bell et al, 2009). First, PST seeks to foster a cognitive shift in problem orientation, helping individuals transition from avoidance and hopelessness to a more active and solution-focused mindset, which enhances coping self-efficacy. Second, PST aims to build problem-solving skills by teaching individuals to systematically identify problems, generate solutions, make decisions, and create action plans. This process seeks to strengthen adaptive coping strategies and improves emotional regulation. Third, behavioural activation and problem resolution serves to reinforce long-term resilience, enabling individuals to manage future stressors more effectively and maintain positive mental health outcomes (Nezu et al., 2012).

Efficacy and effectiveness:

PST has demonstrated impact in treating depression across various populations, but with widely varying effects. In an early meta-analysis of 31 studies Malouff et al. (2007) found evidence of PST being significantly more effective than no treatment ($d = 1.37$) and treatment as usual ($d = 0.54$) but not significantly more effective than (varied and unspecified) other *bone fide* treatments ($d = 0.22$). Moderators predicting stronger effects included problem-orientation training, homework assignment, and a developer of PST being engaged in the study. Subsequent reviews have addressed specific populations, including adolescents, adults, older adults, and primary care patients.

Metz et al.'s (2023) systematic review of 25 studies on PST interventions with adolescents and young adults (ages 13–25) found the strongest evidence – with a moderate risk of bias - supporting PST as a stand-alone intervention for use in relation to clinical depression (as opposed to sub-clinical depression or as a preventive measure). This review adopted a narrative synthesis approach due to the heterogeneity of included studies. In amongst the most rigorous of RCTs, Xavier et al. (2019) had the least risk of bias and reported a five-session intervention delivered by an experienced clinician targeting youth at high-risk for suicide had a large impact on suicidal ideation ($d=4.39$), which persisted to follow-up at six-months ($d=3.98$). There were similarly large impacts on depressive symptoms ($d=2.83$), which sustained to follow-up ($d=2.71$). PST used to prevent or treat sub-clinical depression, or a part of a multi-component intervention showed more mixed results, with Metz et al. (2023) noting the likely influence of variability in quality, dosage, and fidelity monitoring, small sample sizes and short follow-up periods.

A systematic review of 22 studies on PST for adult depression similarly found mixed evidence (Gellis & Kenaley, 2008). Seven studies found PST was significantly superior to control (waiting list, usual care or treatment) in reducing depressive symptoms, with effects persisting up to one year. However, two studies which considered the role of drug treatment indicated that PST combined with antidepressants produced more favourable outcomes than PST alone. Inconsistencies in effectiveness were again attributed due to factors such as sample size considerations and variation in methodological rigour (Gellis & Kenaley, 2008).

For older adults, a 2018 meta-analysis (Shang et al., 2021) found that PST had a significant, large effect on reduced depression scores (SMD = -1.06) compared to waitlist controls, indicating its effectiveness for late-life depression.

Finally, a systematic review and meta-analysis of 11 studies of PST for primary care patients with depression and/or anxiety (Zhang et al., 2018) reported a significant moderate treatment effect ($d = 0.67$). PST involving physicians also led to meaningful improvements, though with a smaller effect size than when delivered by mental health providers.

Overall, the PST evidence-base is thus marked by a good range of systematic and meta-analytical reviews (considered high-quality methods for synthesising research), which cover diverse populations (including adolescents, adults, older adults, and primary care patients) and therefore ensure a broad scope of applicability. Many reviews assess the quality of individual studies, addressing key factors like risk of bias, sample size, and methodological rigour.

Nonetheless, there are weaknesses. The reliance on waitlist control as a comparator is a significant limitation. This approach does not account for placebo effects or the natural progression of mental disorders. Comparisons to active treatments (e.g., other psychotherapies or pharmacological interventions) would provide a more robust evaluation of PST's effectiveness. The heterogeneity of studies is a further limitation. Variability in intervention delivery, dosage, and fidelity monitoring across studies complicates the ability to draw definitive conclusions about the optimal implementation of PST. Finally, the existing evidence-based is also marked by a short-term focus, with reviews generally focusing on short-term outcomes, leaving the long-term effectiveness of PST underexplored.

PST has been shown to be effective across diverse populations, including adolescents, adults, older adults, and primary care patients, with significant effects compared to no treatment or treatment as usual in reducing depressive symptoms. Some studies also report sustained benefits of PST on depressive symptoms and suicidal ideation, lasting up to six months or a year. The effectiveness of PST varies widely, with some studies finding it no more effective than other *bona fide* treatments. Methodological concerns, such as small sample sizes, short follow-up periods, and inconsistent rigor, contribute to these inconsistencies. Additionally, the lack of standardization in intervention delivery, dosage, and fidelity monitoring across studies further complicates the evaluation of PST's effectiveness. There is also evidence suggesting that combining PST with antidepressants may yield better outcomes than PST alone, highlighting the need to explore the role of pharmacotherapy. To address these issues, future research should focus on improving methodological rigor, standardizing intervention protocols, investigating moderators and mediators of effectiveness, and exploring the potential benefits of combination treatments. Overall, while PST shows promise as an intervention for clinical depression, further high-quality research is essential to fully understand its efficacy and optimise its implementation.

Relevance to PLE:

PST seeks to empower people with skills to deal with challenging events and their emotional consequences. Despite frequent reports of positive experience of participants with the approach, there is a lack of strong evidence of this, especially regarding PLE engagement in the development of interventions. Henati et al., (2021) reported engagement with potential users in the development of a digital form of PST targeting patients with symptoms of depression or anxiety on the waiting list for treatment in routine psychiatric care, citing positive appraisals of the credibility and usability of the application. Bennet et al. (2021), noting the value of involving clinicians and patients in intervention design, report using a user-centred design approach to support the adoption, reach, and sustained fidelity of PST.

An interviewee with experience of deploying a PST-based intervention in sub-Saharan Africa noted: 'Problem Solving Therapy very much fitted with local idioms of addressing difficulties... helpers naturally ask questions aimed at "opening up the mind" and participants welcomed this'. This interviewee suggested that in such settings people often present with a focus on the problem that is leading to a mental health issue rather than because they feel anxious or depressed, which is coherent with the approach of PST. Verhey et al. (2020) report how the use of lay health workers from within the community fostered trust, familiarity, and increased acceptability of therapy (Verhey et al, 2020).

Use of peers may also promote trust and engagement. A comparative effectiveness study of clinician-supported PST versus peer-supported, self-guided PST among rural older adults with depression in California found that peer-supported PST was a viable alternative, particularly in settings with limited access to clinicians because it offered a comparable level of effectiveness, was acceptable to participants, and was more feasible and sustainable in resource-constrained rural settings. This model helps to overcome barriers such as limited access to mental health professionals, making it an attractive option for expanding mental health care in underserved communities (Hollister et al, 2024).

Resource requirements and cost-effectiveness:

Although PST may be used by health workers with specialism in mental health (i.e. psychiatrists, psychologists etc.) it has also been shown to be well-suited for use in general practice (Pierce, 2021), nursing (Bosmans et al., 2012), counselling and with a wide range of non-specialist providers (Wallén et al., 2021). The common requirements for implementation are a structured treatment plan, relevant worksheets and tools to guide the client through the problem-solving process, establishment of a safe and supportive therapeutic environment, and the client's active participation in identifying and addressing their problems, including commitment to practice skills between sessions.

The cost-effectiveness of the approach depends significantly on therapist/helper costs in the setting, available mechanisms of supervision and costs (and benefits) to a client of attending sessions. In general, research suggests that problem-solving interventions can be cost-effective for treating depression, often demonstrating a positive cost-benefit ratio by significantly reducing depression symptoms while incurring relatively low treatment costs, particularly when delivered in primary care settings or through accessible formats like online therapy. However, the level of cost-effectiveness varies widely depending on the specific intervention design, population studied, and healthcare system context.

For example, a randomised trial evaluated the cost-effectiveness of PST delivered by mental health nurses in primary care compared to usual care (UC) by general practitioners for patients with mental health problems (Bosmans et al., 2012). The results showed no statistically significant differences in clinical outcomes between the two groups after nine months. However, the mean total costs were lower in the PST group (€4795) compared to the UC group (€6857), although this difference was not statistically significant (95% CI: -4698; 359). Indirect costs in the PST group were substantially lower than in the UC group and were the greatest contributor to the difference in total costs. However, this difference was mainly caused by three outliers in the UC group. Cost-effectiveness analysis indicated that PST was a more cost-effective option, with sensitivity analyses supporting this conclusion. Researchers concluded that findings suggest PST delivered by nurses can be a cost-efficient alternative to usual care in primary settings, but further research is needed to confirm its long-term effectiveness and financial sustainability.

In a study of a PST-based intervention in Pakistan with a mean cost per participant of \$1001 (95% CI 968-1031), Alvi et al. (2021) calculated an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio for PST vs. TAU as \$16 254 (95% CI 7116-99 057) per QALY gained. The probability that the intervention was cost-effective in that context was estimated to be between 66% and 83%.

Context, applicability and scalability:

PST has been widely adapted for low-resource settings (in countries such as Sierra Leone, Ethiopia, and Uganda) where mental health service availability is severely constrained. In these contexts, scarce mental health professionals and fragile health systems necessitate alternative approaches that rely on task-sharing and culturally sensitive adaptations. For perinatal populations - women experiencing significant psychosocial stressors during pregnancy and postpartum periods – and those receiving HIV counselling PST has been shown to offer a structured yet flexible framework for addressing depression and anxiety.

A study examining the experiences of HIV clients in Zimbabwe with the Friendship Bench (FB) programme, a PST-based intervention, highlighted its positive impact (Verhey et al, 2020). Sessions provided a safe space to discuss traumatic experiences, including the shock of diagnosis, stigma, family discrimination, and the challenges of poverty and food insecurity. Clients were also reported to appreciate the programme's cultural congruence and its adaptation to the local context, which made therapy more relatable and helped reduce stigma. PST was selected as the foundational intervention of the recently completed TENDAI trial of PST-AD (problem-solving therapy for adherence and depression) using HIV counsellors and nurses to support people living with AIDS and HIV. In Sierra Leone, the problem-solving component of the Friendship Bench model has been tailored to address cultural adaptations and contextual stressors such as post-conflict trauma for women presenting with perinatal psychological distress (Bah et al., 2025). Similarly, adaptations in Ethiopia focused on antenatal depressive symptoms by aligning intervention language and cultural metaphors with local understandings of distress (Bitew et al, 2022). In Uganda Nakku et al. (2021) evaluated a group-based PST intervention delivered by trained midwives to women with perinatal depression. They found clinical response for depression (defined as a 50% or more reduction in symptom scores) with 94% of their participants.

These findings reinforce the potential of PST in limited resource settings, when delivered through community-based approaches, enhancing accessibility, cultural relevance, and community engagement in mental health care. However, these adaptations of PST for programmes in Sierra Leone, Zimbabwe, Ethiopia, and Uganda exemplify both innovative progress and inherent challenges. While these interventions offer feasible, culturally adapted support in contexts where specialised mental health care is inaccessible, they also prompt critical reflection on the limitations of transferring western models to low-resource settings. Future randomised studies are needed to confirm the efficacy of these interventions and genuine potential for scale up. Such studies should examine not only clinical efficacy but also implementation factors critical for scale-up, including optimal training models, supervision requirements, and integration pathways within existing health systems.

Contribution to social justice and equity, diversity and inclusion:

Given the evidence supporting the implementation of PST in low-resource settings, the approach is of clear relevance not only to bridging the gap left by the scarcity of mental health specialists in low-income countries but also offers a practical model for expanding access to care. Research indicates that while the core components of psychological treatments like PST remain consistent, cultural adaptations are being the focus of implementation strategies in diverse countries. For instance, a culturally adapted version of PST for Chinese older adults preserved the therapy's core mechanisms but incorporated cultural themes related to stigma, hierarchical provider-client relationships, and acculturation (Chu et al, 2011). These modifications made PST more understandable and relevant for Chinese elderly individuals.

A primary concern regarding these adapted interventions is their fidelity to the effective principles of PST; while cultural adaptations are essential to ensure relevance and acceptability within local contexts, they also risk diluting the core components that underpin the therapy's proven effectiveness. This tension between maintaining fidelity to the original evidence-based model and making necessary cultural modifications is a core focus for the rigorous implementation science research required in this area.

While PST shows promise for improving individual mental health outcomes, its broader impact on systemic inequities remains uncertain. Structural factors such as poverty, gender inequality, and limited healthcare infrastructure continue to contribute to mental health disparities. Thus, although culturally adapted PST interventions are an encouraging step toward reducing inequity, they need to be integrated into comprehensive strategies that address both individual and systemic determinants of mental health.

Barriers and facilitators to intervention advancement and overview of lessons learned:

Our review supports Bennet et al.'s (2023) view that 'While PST ... is an effective psychotherapy, it is not widely used'. It has 'scaled' in that it has been implemented across a wide range of settings, but its use appears restricted in comparison to many other psychological interventions.

Several factors have facilitated PST advancing in its development for use in such a range of contexts. The approach has a clear claim to be an evidence-based intervention given the many studies that have considered its effectiveness, and it has established its transdiagnostic relevance beyond its principal focus on depression. It has been established that it can be effectively used by both mental health specialists and non-specialists (including peers) and can be implemented in a wide range of formats, including individual, group, by telephone, digitally etc. It has been shown to be accessible across a range of cultural contexts and amendable to contextual adaptation and elaboration (with one interviewee noting '*it is easy to hang other things onto PST, for example, we've added a session on behavioural activation and material on relaxation and sleep management*').

What then are the principal barriers that have prevented it being full scaled and closer to widespread adoption? First among these remains lack of clarity in the evidence-base regarding when and for whom PST is the most effective treatment option. The evidence-base highlights the potential for large impacts, but there is such heterogeneity of findings that it is difficult to specify with confidence the circumstances when, on clinical grounds, PST may be the treatment of choice. Second, the flexibility with which the core problem-solving component of PST can be deployed allows wide variation in the presentation, profiling and evaluation of the intervention. This contributes in turn to the further fragmentation and heterogeneity of the evidence-base. Third, there are few clear examples of PST being fully integrated into a stepped-care model of mental health provision. In low-resource settings in particular – but potentially in high-resource settings also – the explicit integration of PST as a routine form of intervention within a functional, sustainable system of care would be a powerful demonstration of its readiness for adoption. Fourth, a barrier in common with many other psychological interventions, are challenges in training, supervision and retention of personnel to deliver PST, especially again in low-resource settings. As one interviewee noted: '*Maintaining reliable supervision is a major barrier to scaling. A local clinical psychologist has provided group supervision to counsellors every two weeks, with support from international researchers. We're looking at a more sustainable approach, utilising digital technology*'. Integrating training in PST into pre-service training curricula of nurses and other health workers – rather than relying on costly in-service training initiatives – would be a major advance in addressing this barrier.

In terms of overall lessons learned, the cumulative evidence underscores the complex interplay between intervention fidelity and the need for cultural adaptations. Effective PST implementation demands a careful and systematic approach: adaptations must preserve the intervention's core problem-solving mechanisms while ensuring cultural and contextual relevance. Research from diverse settings suggests that task-sharing to non-specialist providers can yield positive outcomes, but sustained success depends on rigorous training, ongoing supervision, and long-term evaluation.

Furthermore, the integration of PST into broader health systems via stepped-care models and digital initiatives represents a practical pathway for scale-up, albeit one that must continuously address socio-cultural issues and structural inequities driving poor mental health outcomes. While PST holds significant promise as a scalable intervention for reducing the mental health treatment gap in low-resource settings, future research must focus on generating long-term efficacy data and refining implementation strategies to ensure that adaptations do not compromise the intervention's integrity and basis for demonstrated clinical impact.

Recommendations for investment:

In terms of addressing gaps in the evidence-base that would potentially support wider scaling and adoption of PST there are three major priorities indicated by the above analysis:

Research Recommendations

- **Consolidation of the existing evidence-base.** There is a need to bring together and summarise the existing research on what factors influence the effectiveness of Problem-Solving Therapy (PST). Specifically, it's important to identify the studies with the highest quality and the least risk of bias to understand the clinical impact of PST on conditions like depression and others. The goal is to examine how certain factors influence the outcomes of PST. These factors include both client characteristics, such as age; gender; condition etc., and intervention characteristics, such as how the therapy is delivered (e.g. in-person vs. online), the setting (e.g. clinic vs. community), and the type of therapist or helper (e.g. professional therapist vs. peer support).
- **Extension of the existing evidence-base in terms of comparative effectiveness and cost.** Current research has primarily established PST's efficacy against minimal or no treatment conditions. This represents a low evidentiary bar that fails to address the more pressing question: how does PST compare to other intervention approaches? This includes transdiagnostic approaches that target multiple mental health concerns simultaneously. Investment in head-to-head comparisons is essential not merely to determine which intervention "works better" but to understand the opportunity costs associated with large-scale PST implementation versus broader approaches. Similarly, current cost-effectiveness analyses of PST typically focus narrowly on intervention delivery costs without accounting for the substantial system-level investments required for sustainable implementation. Research must expand to include comprehensive economic evaluations that capture the true costs of building and maintaining the infrastructure necessary for quality PST delivery at scale and comparator intervention approaches.
- Evaluation of sustainable models of staff training, supervision and retention for PST implementation in low-resource environments. There is significant evidence regarding the potential impact of PST-based interventions delivered by non-specialists in low-resource settings. To translate this promise to substantive health gain in these settings requires robust evidence on sustainable, effective mechanisms of staff training, supervision and support that can be integrated into existing, developing health systems.

Ecosystem Recommendations

Other investments that are warranted based on the preceding review include:

- **'Lessons learned' exercise for deployment of PST-related interventions in the context of perinatal and sexual health provision.** The review has noted a number of independent studies utilising PST-related methods in relation to mental health needs in the context of perinatal and sexual health provision in LMICs. What are the common lessons drawn from these initiatives in terms of such issues as (a) user/PLE engagement in terms of service development; (b) presentation and adaptation of problem-solving strategies in specific contexts; (c) augmentation of PST with other material to address additional needs; and (d) mainstreaming of initiatives within existing health provision?
- **Documenting digital innovations related to the delivery of PST.** The review has highlighted several innovations – principally at the pilot or ideation stage – in using digital technology to support scaling of PST. Bringing together information on innovations – such as 'scaffolding technology' for PST

intervention design or commercial products such as EverMind's ePST – may usefully serve to profile and promote such innovation.

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